

Deliverable 6.3

Report on TCL Ocean Literacy Activities and Blue Justice Stories

Version 1

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Executive Summary

Under Task 6.4 of the EmpowerUs project, titled ‘Ocean Literacy and Outreach’, each Transition Coastal Lab (TCL) was tasked with organising and carrying out at least two Ocean Literacy activities. An amendment was made to include national surveys understanding of society’s relationship with the ocean for each of the six host countries, to increase understanding of how ocean literacy empowers people to tackle the challenges they face, for dissemination through policy briefs that aim to empower policy makers to make more informed decisions regarding the ocean.

EmpowerUs interprets Ocean Literacy as a person’s ‘understanding of what the ocean does for them, and what they can do for the ocean’. Improving societal ocean literacy aims to empower people to make informed decisions that will improve ocean and climate resilience including, but not limited to, their lifestyle choices and practical action for the ocean. Ocean literacy has been dubbed by some to be ‘the enabling factor for success in all ocean issues’, without which we will not be able to achieve the goals of the UN Decade of Ocean Science. Ocean literacy research aims to understand ocean literacy levels, what effects and affects them and how to improve them; ocean literacy activities (or ocean education) aim to strategically improve ocean literacy. The EmpowerUs project evolved an increasing interest in how ocean literacy can be an ‘enabling factor’, empowering communities to engage in dialogues tackle the challenges their face.

The EmpowerUs project uses the concept of empowerment, in line with Avelino (2017), as outlined in Deliverables 3.2 (Spiering et al. 2025a) and 4.2 (Dushkova et al. 2024). We understand empowerment as the process through which actors gain the capacity to mobilise resources and institutions to achieve a goal. The project operates with three dimensions of empowerment: (1) access to resources and institutions, (2) strategies to mobilize them, and 3) the willingness to do so.

This definition was extended to the way ocean literacy surveys and activities were developed. The EmpowerUs goal for this deliverable was use this framework wherever possible, together with empowerment and transitioning needs identified by other work packages (specifically those presented in D3.2, Spiering et al. 2025a), to improve ocean literacy within the TCL communities, empower and inspire local stakeholders and decision makers through building community capacity to engage with ocean-related issues, and foster deeper connections to nature and cultural heritage. In parallel, TCLs collected local Blue Justice stories, which reflect the lived experiences of coastal communities facing challenges and opportunities linked to the blue economy and blue growth. The project added some national and broader context, through ocean literacy research (surveys) centred around empowerment at the national level for each country.

This report first outlines the theoretical frameworks, methodological approaches, and collaborative processes used to co-design and implement these initiatives, in collaboration with ERINN (WP6 lead) and NRI. We then provide an overview of all Ocean Literacy activities conducted across the project, in addition to the ocean literacy resources that were developed and the Blue Justice stories that were gathered. As the project developed, it was clear that parts of other work packages were working with ocean literacy in novel ways that was in keeping with the concept of as an empowerment tool or mechanism for change, and so where appropriate these have also been reported in the current report. Specifically, this includes the photovoice method, used to both research and educate (WP5) and ocean literacy activities that were inherently linked to the results of the TCL pilots (WP2). In conclusion, this report provides good examples of how strategic ocean literacy interventions, that push beyond

knowledge, can be used to catalyse empowering conversations and participation, to tackle coastal transitioning needs.

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1. Setting the Scene – What is Ocean Literacy?

1.1 The Concept of Ocean Literacy

EmpowerUs interprets ocean literacy as a person's 'understanding of what the ocean does for them, and what they can do for the ocean'. An ocean literate citizen, be they a member of the public or a high-level policy maker, is one who can make informed, responsible decisions regarding the sustainable use and conservation of the ocean. Ocean literacy research aims to understand ocean literacy levels, what effects and affects them and how to improve them; ocean literacy activities (or ocean education) aim to strategically improve ocean literacy.

Traditionally, ocean literacy was considered as marine education, which was interpreted by many as a push of knowledge, often targeting children and youth. Marine science projects may deliver their 'outputs' as marine education activities through workshops, one-off school visits and informational leaflets, to often-unreceptive audiences. These more traditional means of education, often with one-off or short-term impact, showcase the more traditional view of ocean literacy, but do not always maximise the potential longer-term impact of working with the evolved concept of ocean literacy that works with wider dimensions. Recent research into the experience of delivering marine education and ocean literacy finds that to achieve a societal understanding of what the ocean does for us, and what we can do for the ocean, we need to reach a range of specific audiences including industry, businesses and government, while also not forgetting the next generations. Ocean literacy research therefore aims to understand ocean literacy levels, what effects and affects them and how to improve them, whilst ocean literacy activities (or ocean education) aim to strategically improve ocean literacy.

Task 6.4 Ocean Literacy and Outreach initially focussed on ocean literacy education, where each of the EmpowerUs TCL teams were upskilled in ocean literacy and relevant place-based ocean literacy activities were co-developed to promote understanding and appreciation of the ocean within the TCL communities. These initiatives aimed to empower and inspire local stakeholders by highlighting the ocean's vital role in society and everyday life and promoting nature-connectedness and local cultural heritage through the activities. However, an amendment was made to include ocean literacy research: national surveys understanding of society's relationship with the ocean for each of the six host countries, to increase understanding of how ocean literacy empowers people to tackle the challenges they face, for dissemination through policy briefs that aim to empower policy makers to make more informed decisions regarding the ocean.

1.2 Ocean Literacy as knowledge – The Principles

The ocean literacy concept was initially rooted in the idea that, in order to be ocean literate, citizens must have an understanding of the 7 Essential Principles of Ocean Science (Santoro et al. 2017, NMEA 2024), all of which are knowledge-based. The 7 principles are as follows:

1. The Earth has one big ocean with many features
2. The ocean and life in the ocean shape the features of Earth
3. The ocean is a major influence on weather and climate
4. The ocean makes Earth habitable
5. The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems
6. The ocean and humans are inextricably interconnected
7. The ocean is largely unexplored

1.3 Evolution of Ocean Literacy and pushing beyond knowledge – The Dimensions

Building on the Ocean Literacy Principles and ocean literacy as knowledge, it is now commonly accepted that the way we absorb, interpret, and use our ocean knowledge is influenced by at least nine other dimensions (McKinley et al., 2023). EmpowerUs wanted its engagement to push beyond the traditional concept of ocean literacy as knowledge, ‘bolt on’ outreach and marine education, and instead asked ‘**How can we improve awareness of ocean literacy amongst the transdisciplinary team and beyond, and make ocean literacy both inclusive and empowering?**’ To answer this question, we developed a strategic approach to design and delivery, utilising the dimensions that influence ocean literacy as a framework by which to ground our desired impact (based on dimensions summarised by McKinley et al., 2023). The ten dimensions of ocean literacy, used as the basis to inform the design and development of ocean literacy activities within the EmpowerUs project, are as follows:

1. **Awareness:** Recognising the ocean's influence on us and our influence on the ocean.
2. **Knowledge:** Understanding the ocean's physical, chemical, and biological processes, and its role in Earth's systems.
3. **Attitudes:** Holding positive or negative feelings and opinions about the ocean and its resources.
4. **Communication:** Effectively sharing knowledge and information about the ocean with others.
5. **Behaviour:** Making responsible choices and taking actions that benefit the ocean and its ecosystems.
6. **Activism:** Engaging in efforts to protect and conserve the ocean and its resources.
7. **‘Emocean’ (Personal or emotional connection):** Recognising and valuing the emotional and psychological benefits derived from the ocean.
8. **Access, experience, and proximity:** Understanding the importance of physical and social access to the coast and ocean, and the influence of proximity on engagement.
9. **Adaptive capacity:** Recognising the need to adapt to changes in the ocean and its environment.
10. **Trust and transparency:** Assessing the reliability and clarity of information related to the ocean.

1.4 Positioning the EmpowerUs approach to ocean literacy around empowerment

Improving societal ocean literacy aims to **empower people** to make informed decisions that will improve ocean and climate resilience including, but not limited to, their lifestyle choices and practical action for the ocean. The EmpowerUs project uses the concept of empowerment, in line with Avelino (2017), as outlined in Deliverables 3.2 (Spiering et al. 2025a) and 4.2 (Duschkova et al. 2024). We understand empowerment as the process through which actors gain the capacity to mobilize resources and institutions to achieve a goal. The project operates with three dimensions of empowerment:

- (1) access to resources and institutions,
- (2) strategies to mobilize them
- (3) and the willingness to do so.

This definition was extended to the way ocean literacy surveys and activities were developed. The EmpowerUs goal for this deliverable was use this framework wherever possible, together with empowerment and transitioning needs identified by other work packages (specifically those presented in D3.2, Spiering et al. 2025a), to improve ocean literacy within the research team, project partners,

TCL communities and higher level decision makers through building community capacity to engage with ocean-related issues, and foster deeper connections to nature and cultural heritage.

1.5 The Concept of Blue Justice

Ocean literacy and Blue Justice are closely interlinked. While ocean literacy traditionally focused on disseminating scientific knowledge about the marine environment (Santoro et al., 2017), we know that this knowledge alone is insufficient to empower communities to engage in equitable ocean governance (Berkes, 2021). Recent approaches, including the evolved dimensions of ocean literacy (McKinley et al., 2023), recognise that the ability of people to make informed choices is influenced by access, emotional connection (emoceans), trust and transparency, attitudes and adaptive capacity, all of which are intertwined with power relations. Blue Justice frames these power relations explicitly, highlighting how marginalised communities are affected by dispossession, inequitable benefits, and exclusion from decision-making (Bennett et al., 2021).

There have been calls for ocean literacy research to consider equity and justice in research but also as a way of working (McRuer et al., 2024), including in the co-production of knowledge and resources (Polejack et al., 2025). Integrating Blue Justice into ocean literacy research and practise therefore expands its scope beyond awareness-raising to include critical reflection on governance, rights, and agency (Linke et al., 2022). Storytelling, participatory workshops, and place-based education can serve simultaneously to build ocean literacy and to surface claims for justice, thereby strengthening both cognitive and transformative capacities in coastal communities. Blue Justice examines how local coastal communities are impacted by the Blue Economy and Blue Growth. It looks at how the Blue Economy/Blue Growth agenda can further marginalise and disadvantage small scale fisheries and other users of the sea through initiatives including industrial fishing, coastal and marine tourism, aquaculture and energy production. Other EmpowerUs work packages have explored how understanding blue justice is an important element of successful transitioning and transformation¹, whilst ocean literacy offers an opportunity to improve the knowledge and awareness to broader society, and could be seen as essentially inseparable lenses and tools, if the goal is transformation.

As part of Task 6.4, each of the EmpowerUs TCLs were responsible for collecting local Blue Justice stories from their communities. These stories are portrayed on an interactive [online EmpowerUs StoryMap](#) that is hosted on the EmpowerUs website and EmpowerCoast Digital Platform.

The development of both the Ocean Literacy activities and Blue Justice stories has been informed by the work of Bennett et al. (2021) who have highlighted ten injustices that may arise as a result of the blue economy and blue growth. These injustices include:

- a) Dispossession, displacement and ocean grabbing,
- b) Environmental justice concerns from pollution and waste,
- c) Environmental degradation and reduction of ecosystem services,
- d) Livelihood impacts for small-scale fishers,

¹ Power and knowledge: Who gets to define the ocean and its uses, whose knowledge counts, and who benefits from ocean narratives is a justice question For more detail see Spiering et al., 2025b (D4.2 participation and equity, narratives and empowerment) and Flannery et al., 2023 (D2.1 power, governance and agency).

- e) Lost access to marine resources needed for food security and well-being,
- f) Inequitable distribution of economic benefits,
- g) Social and cultural impacts,
- h) Marginalisation of women,
- i) Human and Indigenous rights abuses,
- j) Exclusion from governance.

Bennett et al. (2021) also define three distinct types of blue justice that were utilised within EmpowerUs to develop the statements used for the Q-methodology in WP3 (D3.2, Spiering et al. 2025a). This methodology was used to assess TCL needs and feelings of empowerment, with the initial findings being subsequently used to help inform the design of TCL-specific Ocean Literacy activities (see Section 2.2).

2. Methods

2.1 Ocean Literacy Surveys

The International Ocean & Society Survey (OSS) was undertaken in six countries across Europe (Bulgaria, Cyprus, Finland, Ireland, Norway and Spain) between April - May 2025, following the methods described in McRuer et al. (2025). Participants were asked 30 standard questions about their understanding of, and relationship with the ocean, and their willingness to change their lifestyle if they know it will help the ocean. Respondents were also asked 3 additional questions which together reflect how empowered they feel to tackle the general challenges that their communities face, including:

1. Their knowledge they have to tackle the challenges they face,
2. Their willingness to participate in action to help, and
3. Their perceived access to the resources and tools they need.

In addition to the standard OSS and empowerment questions, EmpowerUs also considered the addition of other questions that may be strongly related to peoples' feelings of empowerment to tackle their challenges. For this reason, the Cantril Ladder, an assessment of subjective well-being widely utilised by the World Health Organisation, was also added to the survey: *'Please imagine a ladder with steps numbered from 0 at the bottom to 10 at the top. Suppose we say that the top of the ladder represents the best possible life for you and the bottom of the ladder represents the worst possible life for you. On which step of the ladder would you say that you personally feel you stand at this time, assuming that the higher the step the better you feel about your life. And the lower the step the worse you feel about it. Which step comes closest to the way you feel?'*

The full list of questions asked are available in [Appendix 3](#).

Data collection

To explore the society's relationship with the ocean, the Ocean & Society survey (facilitated by EmpowerUs) targeted 1000 respondents from each of the countries, nationally representative by age, gender and, wherever possible, region or county. To do this, we used an agreement already in place with the Ocean & Society Survey that delivered the online surveys via an overarching

dashboard collating responses from nationally representative survey panels, facilitated by the UK based company FocalData².

EmpowerUs acknowledges that global survey tools like this only provide rapid assessments of a nation's opinion, feelings and perceptions. The Ocean & Society surveys were undertaken by online survey panels, advertised in the main language of each country, therefore inherently biased by language and self-selection to join such a panel. This approach can be a barrier to Leaving No One Behind, as national surveys do not take into account minority views, so more research is needed to account for place specific variations. However, as a late amendment to the EmpowerUs survey, these surveys aimed to capture opinions of empowerment and ocean literacy beyond the local community (TCL) level, to be interpreted in a way that gives decision makers some more national context, to compare to the local experiences of empowerment presented in D3.2 (Spiering et al., 2025).

Understanding society's relationship with the ocean across the six EmpowerUs countries

Initial exploration of the data was undertaken for each country individually. This interpretation aimed to give decision makers a broad understanding of society's:

- General environmental concerns;
- Values associated with the ocean (broadly related to ecosystem services for its functioning, provisioning and cultural benefits);
- Feelings when they think about the health of the ocean (for example, concern and responsibility);
- Perception of the most concerning threats to the ocean;
- Key questions related to ocean literacy (recognition that the ocean influences their daily lives, and that their daily actions influence the ocean);
- Willingness to change their lifestyle if they knew it would help the ocean;
- Suggestions of what would incentivise them to change their lifestyle for the ocean;
- Suggestions of what might strengthen understanding of the ocean;
- Ocean connection (how the ocean makes people feel);
- Barriers in connecting people to the ocean;
- Primary sources of information for learning about the ocean;
- Feelings of who should take significant responsibility to address ocean threats;
- Feelings of trust towards different actors (groups of people, sectors or organisation types) to act to address ocean threats;
- Empowerment to tackle general challenges they face with their community (using three questions on knowledge, willingness and access to resources, grounded in EmpowerUs' definition of empowerment from Avelino, 2017, and adapted from D3.2).

To explore variations in the above perceptions and opinions between different demographic groups, Wilson Score Confidence Intervals were calculated for each question related to the above topics. Demographic groups considered in this analysis were: gender, age, education type and income group (where confidence intervals did not overlap, there was interpreted to be a strong demographic

² Further detail on the Ocean and Society Survey is available here: <https://oceanliteracyresearch.com/ocean-and-society-survey/>

difference in responses). The aim of this analysis was not to explore differences between countries, but instead demographic variability in society's relationship with the ocean within a single country.

Analysis of what may influence peoples' willingness to change their lifestyles if they believe it will help the ocean, and general empowerment to tackle the challenges them and their communities face

Many things may influence willingness to behave a certain way (behavioural intention), and there are many combinations of factors that could be at play, including socio-demographics, social norms, personal values, attitudes, beliefs, and ultimately circumstance will determine whether intention plays out as behaviour (Ajzen 1985). For instance, older people may be known to intend to behave one way, but older people from a different country (with different values) may behave differently; or possibly younger people with environmental education or jobs may intend to behave differently to those unrelated to the environmental sectors, but both will be influenced by their circumstances (such as income) to decide whether to ultimately behave a certain way. The evolved concept of ocean literacy, derived from theoretical frameworks across the social sciences, psychology and geographies, works towards the concept that knowledge alone does not influence ocean-positive behavioural intention, or behaviour, and that there are at least 9 other factors at play. Our analysis sought to understand whether any of the demographics or dimensions of ocean literacy measured in the Ocean & Society Survey can help to understand peoples willingness to change their behaviour for the ocean.

Analysis sought to investigate what factors influence both peoples' willingness to act for the ocean, and more generally, whether four dimensions of ocean literacy (awareness, access, emoceans and trust) and any key demographics influence empowerment of people to tackle their more general community challenges.

Willingness to change their lifestyle for the ocean was measured using the following scalar question:

- In the next 12 months, how willing would you be to change your lifestyle if you knew it would help the ocean? (from 1, not willing to 5, very willing)

Dimensions of empowerment to tackle general challenges they and their community face, each measured on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'to a very great extent':

- Please tell us how you feel about the following statement: 'I have knowledge to overcome challenges in my community'.
- Please tell us what you think about the following statement: 'I am willing to participate in actions that make my community more sustainable.'
- Please tell us how you feel about the following statement: 'I have access to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for me as a person—or for my community—to thrive.'

In total 47 different factors (independent variables) were included in a multiple linear regression model using least squares fit to model peoples' willingness to change their lifestyles if they believe it will help the ocean, and dimensions of general empowerment to tackle their challenges. Variables were related to socio-demographics (8 variables, including whether they work in environmental sectors and subjective well-being), ocean awareness (2 variables), access (9 variables), emoceans (11 variables), and trust in different actors to address ocean threats (12 variables):

- Gender
- Age
- Education level
- Length of residency in the country of questioning
- Distance from the ocean (from where they live)
- Whether their work or education focused on the environment (ocean, water, climate, other)?
- Current household annual income, prior to tax being deducted?
- Well-being (Cantril ladder, measuring overall subjective well-being and life satisfaction)

- Awareness: The extent respondents agree or disagree with: My daily actions influence the ocean
- Awareness: The extent respondents agree or disagree with: The ocean influences my daily activities

- Access: Experience that has made respondents feel more connected to the ocean in the past year: Spending time in, on, or near the ocean
- Access: Experience that has made respondents feel more connected to the ocean in the past year: Arts and culture (e.g., books, music, performance)
- Access: Experience that has made respondents feel more connected to the ocean in the past year: Virtual technology (e.g., gaming)
- Access: Experience that has made respondents feel more connected to the ocean in the past year: Educational course or activity
- Access: Experience that has made respondents feel more connected to the ocean in the past year: Talking with family, friends, peers
- Access: Experience that has made respondents feel more connected to the ocean in the past year: Media (e.g., print, social media, films)
- Access: Experience that has made respondents feel more connected to the ocean in the past year: Public venues (e.g., museums, aquariums, libraries)
- Access: Experience that has made respondents feel more connected to the ocean in the past year: Volunteering (e.g., beach cleans)
- Access: Experience that has made respondents feel more connected to the ocean in the past year: Advocacy (e.g., rallies, letters, petitions)

- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Excited
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Nostalgic
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Awed
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Calm
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Grateful
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Connected
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Curious
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Anxious
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Fearful
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Unwelcome
- Emocean (feelings when you think about the ocean): Uninterested

- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Individuals
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Local communities and small businesses
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Government
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Environmental groups or non-profit organizations
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Industry and big businesses
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Indigenous leaders and communities
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Universities and research institutions
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Media
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Foundations or charities
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: The United Nations
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: National environmental authorities
- Trust in the following group to take action to address ocean threats: Schools and curriculum developers

To fit the model, one country had to be removed so Cyprus was removed due to its small sample size, and lack of nationally representative sample.

Prior to regression analysis to reveal significant predictors of willingness to change lifestyles for the ocean, and empowerment, the data has gone through a coding and pre-processing, with the following main steps:

1. Coding responses for analysis

All ordinal variables have been coded to integer scales to prepare the data for regression. All categorical values that do not have a natural ordinal scale has been coded with each category represented by a dummy/binary-variable, where one of the categories is left out to avoid multicollinearity problems.

For questions where respondents were asked to rank which factors were most important to them, the numerical codes were 'stretched', to reflect that an unranked option is a much lower importance for this person than ranks 1, 2 or 3. For instance, respondents were asked 'When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel?' (Q2). In analysis, we would expect increased connection via a positive emotion to result in increased willingness to change their lifestyle (a positive relationship), or for negative emotions, analysis would expect a negative relationship. Respondents could rank their top three emotions, out of 11 potential feelings. As respondents could only rank 3 of the potential 11 responses, 'unranked' dominated the dataset, which skewed the dataset. Therefore, to model a linear relationship between each emotion (Q2) and people's willingness to change their lifestyles if they knew it would help the ocean (Q9) we applied a 'stretched' coding. Instead of omitting 'unranked' from analysis, or coding unranked as 1, and rank 3 as 2, rank 2 as 3 and rank 1 as 4 (resulting in a heavy skew); analysis needed to take into account that unranked responses did not reflect a 4th rank. The scale was 'stretched' to reflect the potential 11 options, where unranked was coded 0 (where

respondents, given the option, may have ranked the answers anything 1-8), rank 3 was coded 9, rank 2 coded 10, and rank 1 (the highest score) scored 11.

2. Normalisation and Box-Cox-transformation

After remapping/coding, the freeware analysis software **GNU Octave** was used for transformation and analysis. The variables were normalised and transformed using the Box-Cox method to ensure that each variable is as close to a normal distribution with zero mean and variance equal to one.

3. Missing data imputation

To ensure a complete data set, a multiple imputation procedure was used that considers cross-correlation patterns in the data set when imputing missing data.

4. Variation inflation factor analysis

The complete data set was checked for multi-collinearity issues using a variation inflation factor analysis, where variables with variation inflation factors higher than 10 would be removed. In this analysis, it turned out that none of the variables had such high levels of multi-collinearity.

5. Multiple Linear Regression using Least Squares Fit

Several iterations of multiple linear regression were performed where for each iteration, non-significant variables (p-values larger than 0,05) were removed for the next regression. After three iterations, a stable model was produced that revealed all the independent variables that show a significant relationship with the response variables.

The results present the results of the third iteration modelled, showing significant factors (predictors or independent variables) that affect the four factors we set out to analyse (responses, or dependent variables):

- How willing people are to change their lifestyles if they knew it would help the ocean (Q9).

Dimensions of empowerment to tackle general challenges they and their community face:

- How much knowledge people feel they have to overcome challenges in their community (Q48).
- How willing people are to participate in actions that make their community more sustainable (Q53).
- How much access people feel they have to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for them as a person—or for their community—to thrive (Q54).

2.2 Ocean literacy activities delivered with TCL Partners

EmpowerUs committed to delivering two ocean literacy activities in each TCL, and twelve resources across the project. The project wanted to ensure meaningful engagement, that aligned both with the overarching project goals and the evolved concept of ocean literacy (Morris-Webb et al. 2025b), and the first step to doing this was to align the consortiums' understanding of ocean literacy. TCL partners were actively engaged in ocean literacy development throughout the project duration. In preparation for engaging with TCL partners in ocean literacy, ERINN completed the IOC-UNESCO Ocean Literacy MOOC and subsequently invited TCL partners to complete the course. ERINN conducted a review of

existing ocean literacy resources and developed an online repository of resources, which was shared on the project SharePoint with TCL partners in August 2023. The repository included existing ocean literacy courses, resources, events and networks that are of relevance to the TCLs and was updated on a regular basis as the TCLs prepared to organise their own ocean literacy activities. An internal interactive ocean literacy workshop was organised by ERINN at the end of August 2023. ERINN presented the repository of ocean literacy resources and TCLs explored their initial ideas and existing needs for Ocean Literacy Activities during the workshop. ERINN and NRI organised and held individual follow-up meetings from December 2023 – January 2024 with each TCL to discuss TCL ocean literacy plans and activities in more depth. A follow-up workshop was carried out in February 2024 to explore how the design and development of ocean literacy activities and resources could be informed using knowledge already generated within the project from WP3 surrounding empowerment needs in relation to Blue Justice (presented in D3.2, Spiering et al., 2025a).

Thereafter, frequent check-ins were arranged with TCL partners to discuss their progress with ocean literacy in the project and to explore what needs they had and how they could be supported. To ensure that all those involved with the production of ocean literacy activities and materials had the tools and information they needed, check-ins followed the EmpowerUs working definition of empowerment to attain a goal (Avelino, 2017; D3.2 Spiering et al. 2025a, and D4.2, Duschkova et al. 2024) and therefore focused on the following:

- a. Support with **access** to resources, including signposting to relevant resources and examples, finance and support,
- b. An adaptable **strategy** to mobilise their ocean literacy, constructed around both the knowledge generated in early stages of EmpowerUs about empowerment needs in each community, and how this could be linked to ocean literacy dimensions (see Section 1.3),
- c. Nurture a **willingness** to deliver meaningful ocean literacy by working on the awareness of issues and potential positive solutions relevant to both their needs and ocean literacy.

This method is further detailed in D5.2 'Chapter 11 Strategic Ocean Literacy: Ensuring European project activities meaningfully align with both their ambitions and the evolved concept of ocean literacy' in the [Handbook of Inclusive Methodologies \(Morris-Webb et al. 2025b\)](#), and was presented at the One Ocean Science Congress (Morris-Webb et al. 2025a).

Completed ocean literacy activities were captured by TCLs using an activity reporting template developed by ERINN (see Appendix 1).

2.3 Blue Justice Stories

In order to facilitate the collection of Blue Justice stories in the local TCL communities, a story collection template was developed by ERINN, with inputs from NRI, AAU and RURALIS. The story collection template was shared with TCL partners, in addition to a consent form that was distributed for stories that involved engagement with coastal community members (see Appendix 2).

2.4 Photovoice Methodology

Photovoice is a participatory research method that invites participants to act as co-investigators through visualising narratives via photography. The research method was developed by Wang & Burris (1997) and seeks to deepen understanding of a community by developing knowledge to address and uncover issues while building local capacity.

Photovoice was employed in the EmpowerUs project for empirical data collection and to allow broader TCL participation. The participants were presented with prompts – in relation to the overarching vision to ‘re-direct the Blue Economy to support thriving coastal communities’- and invited to reflect on enabling and preventing mechanisms to connect to the sea, benefit from the sea/and or its resources, and/or promote community wellbeing or vitality. Furthermore, building on the Leave No One Behind principles, the photovoice method was utilised to recruit participants from ‘hard-to-reach’ groups, e.g., women and youth. The groups classified as ‘hard-to-reach’ groups were groups that had previously been observed to have lower levels of representation in project-related activities, such as workshops.

Participants were, before data collection, presented with an instruction sheet and prompts that were translated into both local and minority languages for the respective TCLs. Participants were asked to photograph or collect 3-5 images, with accompanying written narratives, and encouraged to capture what they thought should be photographed, documented, and analysed from their community. A more detailed description of the Photovoice method in the EmpowerUs project can be found in [D5.2 Handbook of Inclusive Methodologies](#).

The participants' images and narratives were uploaded to a digital portal, which was available in eight languages. Data collected through the photovoice method were inductively qualitatively coded in NVivo 14 to analyse the participants' responses based on the overarching vision, visual features, and emotions. Images and narratives that had been given consent to be shared were exhibited in local TCL events and featured in project publications.

2.5 Analysis of the dimensions of Ocean Literacy nurtured by EmpowerUs

The EmpowerUs project aimed to push its ocean literacy related activities beyond knowledge, and we sought to evaluate our success across the project. Section 2.2 outlined the way that we structured dialogues with activity organisers, encouraging them to consider targeting their activities to specific societal groups (such as area planners, municipality decision makers or even policy makers, in addition to general members of the public). We asked them to consider whether they could work with any of the dimensions of ocean literacy to touch the hearts and minds of their audience, reaching beyond knowledge (Section 1.3, McKinley et al. 2023). All activities organised by TCL required completion of a ‘reporting form’, which included specific questions on which dimensions did they design for, how did they aim to empower this dimension, and did they think they were successful at empowering this dimension (Appendix 1). Unfortunately, research fatigue amongst the organisers meant that not all this information could be collated in the detail we had hoped.

Each targeted ocean literacy activity was scored 0-3 for each of the 10 dimensions (Section 1.3), where a score of 0 reflected that this activity made no contribution to this dimension; 1 was not the focus of the activity, but may be a side impact, 2 indicated some deliberate focus and 3 represented that this was a strong or main focus of activity (often activities had more than one main focus). For example, the MarInfluencers event in Spain taught students to make a podcast about the ocean, scoring 3 for the communication dimension; conversely branded pin badges were given out as prizes at the Hekta på Træna treasure hunt in Norway, to encourage a continued conversation about what they learned at the event, and this was scored as 1 for communication. Total scores were then averaged across activities to provide a visual summary of how the project worked towards the dimensions of ocean literacy through its targeted activities, with a maximum score of 3 for each dimension.

At the end of the project, we could look at how many direct ocean literacy activities, specific pilot activities, research projects (such as photovoice), and resources sought to nurture the different dimensions of ocean literacy. This aims to provide a broad-brush evaluation of how EmpowerUs has delivered ocean literacy strategically across the three-year project.

3. National Ocean Literacy Surveys

In April and May 2025, 5,425 people were surveyed across the 6 EmpowerUs countries. National representation was attained by age, gender and region for Bulgaria (n= 1,106), Ireland (n= 1,039), Norway (n= 1,003) and Spain (n= 1,036). Finland attained representation by age and gender (n= 1,025), but the survey (like to population) was dominated by city dwellers and there were no panel respondents from Åland. Cyprus is known to be a difficult country to survey with online surveys, and only attained a total sample of 216 people, so data was weighted for national representation by gender and age.

EmpowerUs acknowledges that global survey tools like this only provide rapid assessments of a nation's opinion, feelings and perceptions. The Ocean & Society surveys were undertaken by online survey panels, advertised in the main language of each country, therefore inherently biased by language and self-selection to join such a panel. This approach can be a barrier to Leaving No One Behind, as national surveys do not take into account minority views, so more research is needed to account for place specific variations. For example, the Finnish data was biased by Finnish speakers, in a country where Swedish speaking residents dominate several coastal regions and the autonomous region of Åland, in total accounting for 5.2% of the Finnish population; and the Cypriot data could not attain national representation as online surveys are not popular in Cyprus.

3.1 Understanding society's relationship with the ocean across the six EmpowerUs countries

Basic descriptive statistics and univariate analysis of Wilson Score Confidence were used to explore the raw data related to the below topics of interest:

- General environmental concerns;
- Values associated with the ocean (broadly related to ecosystem services for its functioning, provisioning and cultural benefits);
- Feelings when they think about the health of the ocean (for example, concern and responsibility);
- Perception of the most concerning threats to the ocean;
- Key questions related to ocean literacy (recognition that the ocean influences their daily lives, and that their daily actions influence the ocean);
- Willingness to change their lifestyle if they knew it would help the ocean;
- Suggestions of what would incentivise them to change their lifestyle for the ocean;
- Suggestions of what might strengthen understanding of the ocean;
- Ocean connection (how the ocean makes people feel);
- Barriers in connecting people to the ocean;
- Primary sources of information for learning about the ocean;
- Feelings of who should take significant responsibility to address ocean threats;
- Feelings of trust towards different actors (groups of people, sectors or organisation types) to act to address ocean threats;
- Empowerment to tackle general challenges they face with their community (utilising three questions on knowledge, willingness and access to resources, grounded in EmpowerUs' definition of empowerment from Avelino, 2017, and adapted from D3.2, Spiering et al. 2025a).

Summaries of the raw data are presented with key resulting recommendations in policy briefs for each country. A seventh, overarching policy brief, brought together the knowledge from all countries for European and International policy and decision makers, funders and other research projects (see Figure 1 for the summary of this policy brief). All policy briefs are available via the [EmpowerUs resources pages](#), or individually following the links below:

- [EmpowerUs \(2025\) European Ocean Literacy Needs for an Empowered and Resilient Future. EmpowerUs Policy Brief Series. Horizon Europe Project 101059957:](#)
- [Bulgaria;](#)
- [Cyprus;](#)
- [Finland;](#)
- [Ireland;](#)
- [Norway;](#)
- [Spain.](#)

Summaries of all datasets are available via the Ocean & Society Survey combined dashboard, and full data is freely available by request from the same location <https://oceanliteracyresearch.com/ocean-and-society-survey/>.

However, multivariate analysis across countries was required to investigate real demographic differences (when other factors are taken into account) in peoples willingness to change their lifestyles for the ocean ([section 3.2](#)), or feelings of general empowerment to overcome the challenges they and their communities face ([section 3.3](#)). This deliverable focuses on this deeper analysis in Sections 3.2 and 3.3 below.

Ocean Literacy Needs for an Empowered and Resilient Future

Ocean Literacy is an ‘understanding of what the ocean does for us, and what we can do for the ocean’.

Improving societal ocean literacy aims to **empower people to make informed decisions that will improve ocean and climate resilience** including, but not limited to, their lifestyle choices and practical action for the ocean.

Ocean literacy research aims to understand ocean literacy levels, what effects and affects them and how to improve them.

Ocean education (or ocean literacy activities) aims to strategically improve ocean literacy.

OCEAN LITERACY

- Ocean and local waterway health is the **4th most important environmental topic** to address.
- **Women value the benefits the ocean provides more highly than men.** This varies by country, age, income and education level.
- **48% feel calm** when they think about the ocean.
- **66% are concerned** when they think about the health of the ocean and waterways.
- **74% are willing to change** their lifestyle if they think it will help the ocean, but **25% want government resources** to help them achieve this.
- **Industry, big business, government and media are not trusted** to act to address ocean threats.

COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT

- **90% feel they have at least some knowledge** they need to overcome challenges their community faces.
- **92% are willing to take action** to help their community be more sustainable
- **22% feel they do not have, or do not know if they have, access to the resources** they need to help their community.
- People who left education after high school and those of low incomes more commonly reported that they did not have access to the resources they need, compared to those of higher education and incomes

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Facilitate development of national ocean literacy strategies and networks**, including industry as well as individuals.
- **Leave No One Behind: Support ocean literacy and place-based research** to develop strategic communication plans.
- **Fund transdisciplinary research projects that explore what resources are needed** to empower communities to tackle their challenges.
- **Give projects longevity** for ongoing access and support to resources communities need.

Policy Drivers

Sustainable Development Goals, **United Nations Decade of Ocean Science: ‘Restore society’s relationship with the ocean’**, UNESCO **Barcelona Statement**, **European Ocean Pact** prioritises restoring ocean health, supporting coastal communities and advancing knowledge.

Figure 1: Summary of results and recommendations v ocean literacy needs for an empowered and resilient future, from Ocean & Society Surveys in Bulgaria, Cyprus, Finland, Ireland, Norway and Spain (EmpowerUs, 2025). The full series of policy briefs is available at <https://empowerus-project.eu/resources/>.

3.2 Analysis of what influences willingness to change peoples' lifestyles if they believe it will help the ocean

Overall, 74% of respondents were fairly or very willing to change their lifestyles if they knew it would help the ocean, whilst 18% were undecided and 2% were not willing. Overall, the raw data shows that Finnish respondents were less willing than other countries, but there was no significant difference in willingness (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Summary of respondents' willingness to change their lifestyles for the ocean across the EmpowerUs countries. In the next 12 months, how willing would you be to change your lifestyle if you knew it would help the ocean?

In total 47 different factors (independent variables, 12 related to socio-demographics, and 35 related to ocean awareness, ocean access, emotions and trust) were included in a multiple linear regression model using least squares fit to model peoples' willingness to change their lifestyles if they believe it will help the ocean. Of the 28 significant factors identified, 7 were related to socio-demographics and well-being, whilst 21 were related to dimensions of ocean literacy.

Table 1 presents the results of the third iteration of multiple linear regression models, showing 28 significant factors (predictors or independent variables) that affect the how willing people are to change their lifestyles if they knew it would help the ocean (Q9) after all the other independent variables are held constant (N=5425). This model explains only 31% of the variance in the data, which means that other factors (not modelled here) affect people's willingness to change their behaviour for the ocean.

After all other factors are taken into account, Norwegian respondents were significantly more willing to change their lifestyles for the ocean than the respondents of other nations (Table 1: β 0.131, $p < 0.001$), followed by Ireland (β 0.101, $p < 0.001$) and Bulgaria (β 0.072, $p < 0.001$). Beyond country of residence, age was the strongest socio-demographic predictor (β 0.082, $p < 0.001$), but with a smaller influence on willingness than several of the ocean literacy dimensions. Women, respondents of higher well-being, and people of longer residency in the country also showed slightly, but significantly, higher willingness to change their lifestyles than others (β 0.02, $p < 0.05$).

However, holding all the countries and other factors constant, both measures of ocean awareness; four related to access, or connection, to the ocean; 8 emotions and 3 measures of trust all showed slight, but highly significant relationships to peoples' willingness to change their lifestyles for the ocean ($p < 0.001$).

Ocean Awareness: The strongest predictor of peoples' willingness to change their lifestyle for the ocean is that their daily actions influence the ocean (β 0.200, $p < 0.001$). A one step increase in their agreement with the statement 'my daily actions influence the ocean' (5 points from disagree to agree) there is a 0.2 increase on the willingness scale (5 points from not willing to very willing). Awareness that 'the ocean influences my daily activities' was also a highly significant predictor (β 0.095, $p < 0.001$).

Ocean Access: Taking part in advocacy and volunteering were the strongest kinds of ocean access and connection influencing people's willingness to change their lifestyles, which may not be surprising given they are likely very connected to ocean issues. Talking about the ocean with family, friends and peers and spending time in, on or near the ocean were both also highly significant predictors. Surprisingly, there was a slight but significant negative relationship between the number of people who felt that virtual technology (eg: gaming) had made them feel more connected to the ocean in the past year, and their willingness to change their lifestyles (β -0.040, $p < 0.05$).

Emoceans: Emoceans, or emotional connection, to the ocean accounted for 10 of the 28 significant factors affecting peoples' willingness to change their lifestyles for the ocean. Perhaps surprisingly, higher anxiety around the ocean was slightly, but highly significantly, positively related to their willingness to change (β 0.101, $p < 0.001$), whilst feelings of calm, being connected, gratitude, feeling awed, fear, curiosity, excitement and nostalgia, were also positively related to peoples' willingness. Unsurprisingly, feelings of uninterest was slightly negatively related to peoples' willingness to change their lifestyle for the ocean (β -0.032, $p < 0.01$).

Trust in actors to act to address ocean threats: Trust in environmental groups and non-profits to act to address ocean threats was the third strongest predictor, positively related to people's willingness to change their lifestyle for the ocean (β 0.112, $p < 0.001$). Trust in universities and research institutes was also positively correlated (β 0.061, $p < 0.001$). Possibly the most surprising result of modelling, was that after all other factors are taken into account, there is a negative relationship between people's trust in Government to act to address ocean threats, and their willingness to change their lifestyles if they knew it would help the ocean (β -0.057, $p < 0.001$). This may indicate that the more people trust Government to act, the less likely they are to take personal responsibility.

Table 1: Factors showing statistically significant relationships with people’s willingness to change their lifestyles if they knew it would help the ocean in Bulgaria, Ireland, Finland, Norway and Spain. Results from the third iteration of a multiple linear regression model using least squares fit. Goodness-of-Fit Statistics: R^2 0.314, $p < 0.001$; f -value 0.689. β = regression coefficient, p = significance, NaN = not significant and removed from final model. $N=5425$.

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
	<i>Constant</i>	0.044	<0.001
Awareness	Q14.2 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? My daily actions influence the ocean	0.200	<0.001
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Norway	0.131	<0.001
Trust	Q19.4 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Environmental groups or non-profit organizations	0.122	<0.001
Access	Q5.9 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Advocacy (e.g., rallies, letters, petitions)	0.119	<0.001
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Ireland	0.101	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Anxious	0.101	<0.001
Access	Q5.8 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Volunteering (e.g., beach cleans)	0.096	<0.001
Awareness	Q14.3 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? The ocean influences my daily activities	0.095	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Calm	0.090	<0.001
Socio-demo	A3 What is your age?	0.082	<0.001
Access	Q5.5 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Talking with family, friends, peers	0.080	<0.001
Access	Q5.1 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Spending time in, on, or near the ocean	0.076	<0.001
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Bulgaria	0.072	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Connected	0.068	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Grateful	0.065	<0.001
Trust	Q19.7 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Universities and research institutions	0.061	<0.001

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Awed	0.060	<0.001
Trust	Q19.3 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Government	-0.057	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Fearful	0.051	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Curious	0.048	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Excited	0.048	<0.001
Trust	Q19.10 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? The United Nations	0.049	<0.01
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Uninterested	-0.032	<0.01
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Nostalgic	0.035	<0.01
Socio-demo	A2 Which of the following best describes your current gender identity?	0.027	<0.05
Access	Q5.3 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Virtual technology (e.g., gaming)	-0.040	<0.05
Socio-demo	Q49.1 Please imagine a ladder with steps numbered from 0 at the bottom to 10 at the top. Suppose that the top of the ladder represents the best possible life for you, and the bottom represents the worst possible life for you. On which step of the ladder would you say you personally feel you are at the moment, assuming that the higher the step, the better you feel about your life, and the lower the step, the worse you feel about it? Which step is closest to how you feel? Step	0.024	<0.05
Socio-demo	Q21 How long have you lived in this country?	0.024	<0.05
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Finland	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Spain	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A16 What is your highest level of education?	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Unwelcome	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.2 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Arts and culture (e.g., books, music, performance)	NaN	NaN

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Access	Q5.4 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Educational course or activity	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.6 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Media (e.g., print, social media, films)	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.7 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Public venues (e.g., museums, aquariums, libraries)	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.1 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Individuals	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.2 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Local communities and small businesses	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.5 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Industry and big businesses	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.6 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Indigenous leaders and communities	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.8 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Media	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.9 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Foundations or charities	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.11 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? National environmental authorities	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.12 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Schools and curriculum developers	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	Q22 How would you best describe where you live in relation to the ocean?	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	Q27 Has your work or education focused on the environment (ocean, water, climate, other)?	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	Q28 What is your current household annual income, prior to tax being deducted?	NaN	NaN

¹ A β -coefficient of 1 would mean that for a one standard deviation increase in this factor, the response variable (willingness) is predicted to increase by one standard deviation, holding all other variables constant.

3.3 Analysis of what may influence general empowerment to tackle the challenges people and their communities face

Overall respondents felt moderately empowered to tackle the challenges they and their communities face. 90% of respondents feel they have at least some knowledge they need to overcome challenges their community faces and 92% are willing to take action to help their community be more sustainable. However, on average people feel they had a small extent of access to the resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for them as a person—or for their community—to thrive. 22% feel they do not have, or do not know if they have, access to the resources they need to help their community. Overall, the raw data shows that Finnish and Irish respondents feel least empowered in this dimension (access), whilst Spanish respondents felt moderately more empowered (Figure 3).

Univariate analysis of Wilson Score Confidence Intervals for each demographic group found that people who left education after high school and those of low incomes more commonly reported that they did not have access to the resources they need, compared to those of higher education and incomes. Multivariate analysis across countries was required to see if these differences are real when other factors are taken into account (such as age, gender and country).

The results below present the outputs of the third iteration of multiple linear regression models, showing significant factors (predictors or independent variables) that affect the three dimensions of empowerment to tackle general challenges they and their community face:

- Q48: How much knowledge people feel they have to overcome challenges in their community.
- Q53: How willing people are to participate in actions that make their community more sustainable.
- Q54: How much access people feel they have to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for them as a person—or for their community—to thrive.

The same 47 factors (independent variables, 12 related to socio-demographics, and 35 related to ocean awareness, ocean access, oceans and trust) were included in a multiple linear regression model using least squares fit to model what might influence these three pillars of empowerment. As these questions are directed at general empowerment, rather than empowerment to tackle ocean related goals, we expect socio-demographics to be of higher influence. However, we have included the same dimensions of ocean literacy, as human-nature connection and environmental awareness may also help people feel empowered to tackle wider sustainability goals.

These results provide some national context of what empowerment along these dimensions looks like at national levels, and what influences these feelings of empowerment, to augment work done in D3.2 (Spiering et al., 2025a). D3.2, successes and failures of empowerment based on Q-method, asked similar questions to evaluate how EmpowerUs has empowered those involved with the TCL pilots.

Figure 3: Summary of respondents' willingness to change their lifestyles for the ocean across the EmpowerUs countries. In the next 12 months, how willing would you be to change your lifestyle if you knew it would help the ocean?

Factors related to how much knowledge people feel they have to overcome challenges in their community

Table 2.1 in Appendix 4 presents the full results of the third iteration of multiple linear regression models, showing 21 significant factors (predictors or independent variables) that affect peoples perception of knowledge to overcome their challenges, after all the other independent variables are held constant (N=5155). Of the 21 significant factors identified, 11 were related to socio-demographics and well-being, whilst 10 were related to dimensions of ocean literacy. This model explains only 17.5% of the variance in the data, which means that other factors (not modelled here) may be more important in peoples' perception of the knowledge they hold.

Socio-demographics were overall the dominant drivers influencing peoples' self-perceived knowledge to overcome challenges people face in their community, with 11 significant factors identified (out of 21). The most significant relationships were found to be that Irish respondents felt they had significantly less knowledge than other countries (β -0.280, $p < 0.001$), followed by Finnish respondents (β -0.162, $p < 0.001$), and Spanish respondents (β -0.128, $p < 0.001$).

Beyond country factors, the next strongest influencer was well-being; those with higher well-being felt they had more of the knowledge they need (β 0.130, $p < 0.001$). There was also positive relationships between knowledge people believe they have to overcome the challenges their communities face and education level (from high school, to technical training to university and college education, β 0.099, $p < 0.001$), household income (β 0.096, $p < 0.001$) and length of residency in this country (β 0.061, $p < 0.001$).

However, holding all the countries and other factors constant, there were some relationships between dimensions of ocean literacy and peoples' belief of whether they have the knowledge to overcome challenges in their community.

Ocean Awareness: Awareness that 'the ocean influences my daily activities' had a weak but highly significant positive relationship: the more aware people were of this, the more knowledge they felt they had to tackle their general challenges (β 0.092, $p < 0.001$).

Access: There was also a highly significant relationship between peoples' experiences of connecting to the ocean through arts and culture (books, music and performance) and knowledge (β 0.061, $p < 0.001$). Positive experiences of connecting to the ocean through media, spending time in, on or near the ocean were also positively related to feelings of having knowledge to tackle community challenges.

Emotions of feeling connected (β 0.044, $p < 0.01$), excited (β 0.033, $p < 0.01$), awe / wonder (β 0.029, $p < 0.05$) and curious (β 0.027, $p < 0.05$) about the ocean were also positively related to feelings that people had the knowledge they need to tackle the challenges their communities face.

Trust: Increasing trust in indigenous leaders and communities, universities and research institutes were also positive influencers (β 0.04, $p < 0.01$).

Factors related to how willing people are to participate in actions that make their community more sustainable

Table 2.2 in Appendix 4 presents the full results of the third iteration of multiple linear regression models, finding 25 significant factors (predictors or independent variables) that affect peoples' willingness to participate in actions that make their community more sustainable, after all the other independent variables are held constant (N=5227). This model explains 23.3% of the variance in the data, which means that other factors (not modelled here) may be more important in peoples' willingness to take part in such actions. Of the 25 significant factors identified, 6 were related to socio-demographics and well-being, whilst 19 were related to dimensions of ocean literacy.

Finnish respondents appeared slightly, but significantly, less willing than other than other countries when other factors were taken into account (β -0.065, $p < 0.001$). People's willingness to engage in community sustainability efforts was slightly, but significantly, positively influenced by time spent living in the country (β 0.063, $p < 0.001$), education (β 0.063, $p < 0.001$), well-being (β 0.056, $p < 0.001$) and household income (β 0.052, $p < 0.001$). However, there was a negative relationship between age and people's willingness to participate (β 0.063, $p < 0.001$), with younger people more willing than older people when other factors are held constant.

However, holding all the countries and other factors constant, elements of ocean access, awareness, trust and emoceans comprised the seven of the top 10 strongest and highly significant relationships with peoples' willingness to participate in actions that make their community more sustainable.

Ocean Awareness: Awareness that 'my daily actions influence the ocean' (β 0.118, $p < 0.001$) and 'the ocean influences my daily activities' (β 0.103, $p < 0.001$), were two of three strongest relationships identified: the more aware people were of these, the more willing they were to participate for community sustainability.

Access: Perhaps unsurprisingly but also reassuringly, people who felt more connected to the ocean through volunteering in the past 12 months, was the strongest predictor of willingness to participate in future actions to help their community be more sustainable (β 0.128, $p < 0.001$). Positive experiences of connecting to the ocean through advocacy (e.g., rallies, letters and petitions, β 0.055, $p < 0.01$), talking with family, friends and peers (β 0.050, $p < 0.01$), and spending time in, on or near the ocean (β 0.040, $p < 0.01$) were showed weaker yet significant positive relationships to willingness to participate in actions for community sustainability.

Emoceans: Eight emoceans were found to be positively related to peoples' willingness to participate in actions to make their community sustainable (feeling anxious β 0.074, $p < 0.001$, grateful β 0.072, $p < 0.001$, excited β 0.062, $p < 0.001$, curious β 0.055, $p < 0.001$, fearful β 0.054, $p < 0.001$, in awe / wonder β 0.052, $p < 0.001$, connected β 0.052, $p < 0.001$ and calm β 0.041, $p < 0.01$). Conversely, people who were uninterested in the ocean were significantly less likely to be willing to participate in actions for community sustainability (β -0.031, $p < 0.05$).

Trust: The eight strongest relationship that potentially influences peoples' willingness to participate in actions to make their community more sustainable was their level of trust in Government to act to address ocean threats: the higher their trust in Government, the lower their willingness to participate (β -0.065, $p < 0.001$). Positive relationships were identified between willingness to participate and

higher trust in environmental groups and non-profit organisations (β 0.087, $p < 0.001$), universities and research institutions (β 0.057, $p < 0.001$) and indigenous leaders and communities (β 0.033, $p < 0.05$).

Factors related to how much access people feel they have to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for them as a person—or for their community—to thrive

Table 2.3 in Appendix 4 presents the full results of the third iteration of multiple linear regression models, showing 15 significant factors (predictors or independent variables) that affect peoples' feelings of how much they have to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for them as a person—or for their community—to thrive, after all the other independent variables are held constant ($N=4987$). This model explains only 18.8% of the variance in the data, which means that other factors (not modelled here) may be more important in peoples' perceived access to resources they need. Of the 15 significant factors identified, 7 were related to socio-demographics and well-being, whilst 8 were related to dimensions of ocean literacy.

Norwegian respondents felt they had significantly more access to the resources they need than other countries (β 0.079, $p < 0.001$), followed by Spanish respondents (β 0.056, $p < 0.001$).

Subjective well-being was the strongest and most significant predictor of peoples' perceptions of how much access they have to the resources they need to help them and their communities thrive (β 0.201, $p < 0.001$). Positive relationships were also found between the access to resources respondents believe they have and household income (β 0.074, $p < 0.001$), education level (from high school, to technical training to university and college education, β 0.053, $p < 0.001$) and whether respondents' work or education had focused on the environment (ocean, water, climate or other, β 0.030, $p < 0.05$). There was a negative relationship between age and feelings of having the access they need, indicative that older people felt they had lower access than younger people (β -0.068, $p < 0.001$).

However, holding all the countries and other factors constant, there were some relationships between dimensions of ocean literacy and peoples' how much access people feel they have to the resources they need to help them and their communities thrive.

Ocean Awareness: Awareness that 'the ocean influences my daily activities' was the third strongest predictor of peoples' access to resources: the more aware people were of this, the more access they felt they had to the resources they and their communities need to thrive (β 0.105, $p < 0.001$).

Access: The second strongest relationship found was that people who had recently felt more highly connected to the ocean through educational courses and activities than others, also felt that they had higher access to resources (β 0.109, $p < 0.001$). Significant positive relationships were also identified between how much access to resources people felt they had and their positive experiences of connecting to the ocean through virtual technology (β 0.065, $p < 0.001$), arts and culture (β 0.059, $p < 0.01$), and ocean advocacy (β 0.042, $p < 0.01$). Feeling more positively connected with the ocean through spending time in, on or near it, was negatively related to feelings of more access to the resources they need to thrive (β -0.063, $p < 0.001$).

Emoceans: No emoceans were found to significantly influence peoples' feelings of how much they have to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for them as a person—or for their community—to thrive.

Trust: Higher trust in local communities and small businesses to act to address local threats (β 0.051, $p < 0.001$), and indigenous leaders and communities (β 0.050, $p < 0.01$), was linked to significantly more access to the resources people need to help them and their community thrive.

4. Ocean Literacy Activities, Resources, Blue Justice Stories and PhotoVoice Results

4.1 Summary of Specific Ocean Literacy Activities across the project

The project aimed to deliver 12 ocean literacy activities (two per TCL), but this was far exceeded as the project gained momentum. Throughout the EmpowerUs project, a total of 27 Ocean Literacy Activities were organised and conducted across the TCLs, with over 1,500 people reached, and an additional 3 activities were arranged that were targeting policy makers, funders and researchers (Table 2).

Table 2. Summary of Ocean Literacy activities carried out by the EmpowerUs Project

TCL	Number of activities	Activity Names	Target audiences	Ocean / blue literacy principles of focus (n)	Dimensions nurtured (n)
<p>Burgas, Bulgaria <i>(note, also freshwater literacy)</i></p>	<p>13</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Science: ‘City Explorers’ in the Sea Garden • By bike from Planetum to Poda • Lagoon Clean Jamboree 2024 • Biodiversity Carnival 2024: ‘Burgas on Three Lakes’ • A Day at Atanasovsko Lake: Burgas on Three Lakes • Twilight Tales: Nocturnal Wildlife in the City • Birthday Celebrations at Atanasovsko Lake Reserve • Atanasovsko Lake new logo competition. • Climate evolution: Are we ready for the new climate? • Lagoon Clean Jamboree 2025: Renew and refresh The Avocet Trail • Biodiversity Carnival 2025: ‘Burgas on Three Lakes and One Sea’ • Green Day: Actions for the Burgas Dune • Launch of the Renovated Avocet Trail <p>+ 1 environmental education event (<i>‘Earth Day Planting with BBF and Chitalishte’</i>)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public & volunteers: children (3-10yrs), teenagers (15-20), families, local residents, cyclists, amateur naturalists, and retirees, local knowledge holders, reflecting a broad spectrum of age groups and backgrounds • Art university students • Teachers & Schools • Visitors & tourists • Tourism operators & guides • Local businesses (including as local service garage employees as ‘stewards’ for the refreshed Avocet trail; and local retail organisations to assist with mowing and maintenance; the staff of a local bank as Burgas Dune action day) • Area planners, councils and the local mayor • Artists • Journalists & media (incl. national TV and newspapers) • Ocean scientists (Institute of Oceanology from Bulgarian Academy of Science) • <i>(even the police had several briefings on the cycle events, to assist their safe passage)</i> • Co-creation / hosting with Regional Inspectorate of Environment and Water – Burgas and Municipality of Burgas, 	<p>6 Principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1. Earth has one big ocean with many features (5) • 2. The ocean and life in the ocean shape the features of the earth (5) • 3. The ocean is a major influence on the weather and climate (4) • 4. The ocean makes Earth habitable (2) • 5. The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems (10) • 6. The ocean and humans are inextricably linked (8) 	<p>10 Dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge (10) • Awareness (12) • Attitudes (10) • Communication (11) • Activism (7) • Behaviour (10) • Emoceans (11) • Access & Experience (9) • Adaptive capacity (1) • Trust & Transparency (4)

TCL	Number of activities	Activity Names	Target audiences	Ocean / blue literacy principles of focus (n)	Dimensions nurtured (n)
			National Arts Academy, local exhibition centre.		
Eastern Limassol Region, Cyprus	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Getting to Know My Coastline Here Only Monachus Workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primary school children and teachers Co-created with CMMI, the Development Agency of Limassol, the Department of Fisheries and Marine Research and Cyprus Institute's PROTEAS research facility 	<p>2 Principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems (2) 6. The ocean and humans are inextricably linked (2) 	<p>9 Dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge (2) Awareness (2) Attitudes (2) Communication (2) Activism (1) Behaviour (2) Emoceans (2) Access & Experience (2) Trust & Transparency (2)
Åland Islands, Finland	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seminar and Field Visit: Importance of Dikes and Waterways on Åland National Fishing Day The Åland Water Stewardship Campaign (and forum) Herring Fishing Exhibition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water and land-owners Farmers, forestry workers, excavator operators, fish conservationists and local government Users of the Sea: coastal residents, second home owners and recreational fishers General public: children, youth and families Museum visitors, targeting tourists but also local schools, politicians, governmental officials and various fisheries stakeholders Engagement was dominated by men, but women and youth did attend some events 	<p>5 Principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Earth has one big ocean with many features (2) 4. The ocean makes Earth habitable (2) 5. The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems (3) 6. The ocean and humans are inextricably linked (4) 7. The ocean is largely unexplored (1) 	<p>10 dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge (4) Awareness (4) Attitudes (4) Communication (3) Activism (1) Behaviour (3) Emoceans (2) Access & Experience (3) Adaptive capacity (3) Trust & Transparency (2)

TCL	Number of activities	Activity Names	Target audiences	Ocean / blue literacy principles of focus (n)	Dimensions nurtured (n)
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-hosting of various aspects by the Fisheries agency from the Government of Åland, the local fisheries conservation NGO, local government, and another project "Smarta vatten (Smart waters)", local angling / 4H-club and Lokalkraft Leader Åland and the Åland Museum for Hunting and Fishing 		
Connemara and the Aran Islands, Ireland	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine Identities Workshop Webinar on Reflections of Marine Identities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local people from around Lettermullan and South Connemara (including older people) Secondary school students (transition year students) Environmental activists / advocates Members of the Irish Ocean Literacy Network People with an interest in ocean literacy (from Ireland, Bangladesh, France, the UK, and the United States) Co-hosted by Údarás na Gaeltachta, Queens University Belfast, The Seaweed Centre, the Lettermullen and Gorumna Heritage Centre (including a musician), and the Irish Ocean Literacy Network. 	<p>1 Principle</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The ocean and humans are inextricably linked (2) 	<p>6 Dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge (2) Awareness (2) Attitudes (2) Communication (2) Emoceans (2) Access & Experience (2)
Norway	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hekta på Træna (Hooked on Træna) 'Matauk' Seminar at Træna Winter Festival: Take Træna by Storm Our Blue Cultural Heritage: The Pole Hunt 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public – adults, families, young and older Visitors and tourists School staff and local knowledge holders Municipality staff Local businesses 	<p>6 Principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The ocean makes Earth habitable (1) 5. The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems (3) 6. The ocean and humans are inextricably linked (3) 	<p>9 Dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge (3) Awareness (3) Attitudes (2) Communication (3) Activism (0) Behaviour (1)

TCL	Number of activities	Activity Names	Target audiences	Ocean / blue literacy principles of focus (n)	Dimensions nurtured (n)
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visiting artists and scientists from elsewhere in Norway • Co-created with the a film maker and local hotel and aquaculture business, local community fishing heritage museum (Kystlaghuset), eider duck museum, seaweed harvester, artist, Mo orienteringsklubb, Polar Circle Outdoor Council (Polarsirkelen Friluftsråd, regional leaders of Stolpejakten Nordland, the national hiking / pole hunt app), TCL Åland team. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emoceans (3) • Access & Experience (3) • Trust & Transparency (1)
<p>Cap de Creus, Spain</p>	<p>3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MarInfluencers • Food Sovereignty Forum • Small-scale Fisheries Pop-up Exhibition (Mobile, ongoing) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High school students. Targetted a diverse high school students with predominance of foreign nationals including Moroccan, Latin American, Russian) • Local authorities • Artisanal fishers from Cap de Creus and surrounding areas • Fish farmers • Environmental activists • Scientists • Farmers and shepherds • Wine growers • Students • Chefs / cooks • The public • Museum visitors • Tourists and visitors to Cap de Creus National Park. 	<p>6 Principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1. Earth has one big ocean with many features (2) • 2. The ocean and life in the ocean shape the features of the earth (2) • 4. The ocean makes Earth habitable (3) • 5. The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems (3) • 6. The ocean and humans are inextricably linked (3) • 7. The ocean is largely unexplored (1) 	<p>10 Dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge (3) • Awareness (3) • Attitudes (3) • Communication (2) • Activism (2) • Behaviour (10) • Emoceans (3) • Access & Experience (2) • Adaptive capacity (1) • Trust & Transparency (1)

TCL	Number of activities	Activity Names	Target audiences	Ocean / blue literacy principles of focus (n)	Dimensions nurtured (n)
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-creation with BlueGreen Vision SL, Oceanographer, Environmental Scientist & Filmmaker, Photographer, Audiovisual Producer, chefs Inspira Gastronomía, Roses Fisher’s Guild Council of Roses, Cap de Creus Natural Park and Emporda (Local Newspaper) 		
Wider reach	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One Ocean Science Congress, presenting to researchers “How strategic ocean literacy can be used to empower coastal communities in their transitions” UNOC Side Event (hosted by the public UNESCO Beyond Borders Pavillion, in collaboration with 16 partners including the Research Council of Norway), “What funders want for ocean literacy, and how to incorporate it into interdisciplinary science projects to increase your impact”. MARE People and the Sea Conference, presenting to researchers “Pushing beyond knowledge to make ocean literacy more empowering whilst Leaving No One Behind” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research consortiums Policy makers Funders UNESCO / IOC Ocean literacy research community National Decade Committees for the UN Decade of Ocean Science Co-hosted with the Research Council for Norway, NTNU and 13 other partners. 	<p>2 Principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The ocean makes Earth habitable (3) 6. The ocean and humans are inextricably linked (3) 	<p>5 Dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness (3) Attitudes (3) Communication (3) Adaptive capacity (3) Trust & Transparency (3)
Total activities:	30				

4.2 Burgas, Bulgaria

The TCL in Burgas, Bulgaria was hosted by the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation, who have a strong interest in environmental education. Many activities undertaken overlapped with the work of the 'Burgas on Three Lakes and One Sea' pilot, and their series of environmental education events was central to their ambitions and in nature were both freshwater and ocean literacy. As there are many overlaps, they have all been reported here.

Ocean Literacy Activity 1 – 'City Explorers' in the Sea Garden (City Explorers event #1)

April 2024

The first Ocean Literacy activity organised by the Bulgarian TCL team took place in Burgas' Sea Garden and focused on engaging citizens in urban biodiversity monitoring through a citizen science event. This initiative was part of the broader EmpowerUs pilot in Burgas and contributed valuable data to ongoing ecological research efforts. The main goal was to inform and empower the public to actively participate in

biodiversity conservation and to highlight the richness of urban and coastal ecosystems, even within city environments. More than 30 participants, including families with children, students, retirees, and amateur naturalists, joined the activity, reflecting a wide range of age groups and backgrounds.

Using standardised monitoring protocols, participants surveyed the plant and animal life in the park and along the nearby beach. Data collection was supported by mobile applications like iNaturalist and Merlin, allowing for real-time species identification and data logging. Participants were also introduced to various field study techniques and biodiversity research equipment through live demonstrations. Collected data, including GPS locations, weather conditions, and photo documentation, were uploaded to a central database and shared on the iNaturalist platform, under the project [Burgas Urban Explorers Bioblitz, April 2024](#).

The event specifically aimed to attract individuals with varying levels of scientific knowledge by offering user-friendly data collection tools such as mobile apps and field guides. The main objective was successfully achieved, which was to present the citizens with the knowledge and opportunity surrounding citizen science. While the primary objective successfully achieved: to introduce participants to the principles and practice of citizen science, certain challenges also surfaced. Although participants enjoyed the experience, many preferred to focus on being outdoors and observing nature rather than actively using the data collection apps. This highlighted the importance of balancing engagement with digital tools and allowing space for informal exploration.

The programme was ambitious and packed with information, which some participants found overwhelming. For future similar activities, the TCL team plan to slow the pace, focus on fewer tools or techniques, and offer more guided, hands-on learning experiences tailored to different levels of familiarity with scientific practices. Despite the challenges, the event successfully raised awareness about urban nature, the sea and coastal ecosystems, and the importance of public participation in

environmental monitoring. It laid a strong foundation for future community-based biodiversity initiatives in Burgas.

Ocean Literacy Activity 2 – By bike from Planetum to Poda

April 2024

As part of the series of [events for Burgas' Green Weekend](#), for this Ocean Literacy activity, 30 cyclists gathered in front of the Planetum Science Centre at the Burgas Passenger Terminal in the Port of Burgas. From there, they embarked on a scenic cycling tour that followed the city's dedicated cycling network, passing Vaya Lake and continuing on to Mandra Lake, where the ride concluded at the Poda Nature Conservation Centre.

Along the way, participants enjoyed views of Burgas' rich natural landscape. The event was designed to raise awareness about local biodiversity and promote the EmpowerUs Bulgarian pilot initiative. The cycling route physically and symbolically connects three key wetland areas around the city. Upon arrival at Poda, cyclists were welcomed into the Poda Information Centre, where they could rest and take part in birdwatching activities. The Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation presented the EmpowerUs project, introduced the Bulgarian pilot, and shared insights about the ecological importance of the three lakes surrounding the city.

The event attracted a diverse group of participants, including 10 teenagers (ages 15–17), children and parents (4 in total) and 16 adults. Cyclists came not only from Burgas but also from nearby towns such as Nova Zagora. Local police provided support throughout the tour, especially at major intersections, ensuring safety for all riders. The cycling event also helped familiarise citizens with the local nature protection NGOs, including the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation and the Bulgarian Society for the Protection of Birds, both active in preserving the Burgas wetlands. The event showcased how accessible, family-friendly experiences like cycling can connect citizens to nature and strengthen support for environmental conservation efforts. The route was thoroughly tested by organisers two days in advance, and several meetings with local police ensured smooth coordination and the safety of all participants.

“It was my first time on a bike in 30 years and it was a wonderful experience and a very nice ride from Burgas to Poda” – Daniela Kaneva, a participant from Nova Zagora.

Ocean Literacy Activity 3 – Lagoon Clean Jamboree 2024

April 2024

To celebrate Earth Day, the Lagoon Clean Jamboree 2024 brought together volunteers, schoolchildren, and local organisations for a full day of environmental action along the Avocet Trail at Atanasovsko Lake. The event was organised by the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation with support from the Regional Inspectorate of Environment and Water – Burgas and the Municipality of Burgas. The event began with an introductory talk about Atanasovsko Lake and the EmpowerUs project, highlighting the importance of the area for biodiversity, conservation, and eco-education. Following the presentation, volunteers participated in a range of impactful activities, such as tree planting, litter collection, cleaning the canal and trail repair and maintenance. A total of 10 new trees were planted, nearly 30 large bags of waste were collected, one information panel was restored, nine educational signs were varnished and given new supports, and the trail and visitor areas were mowed.

Approximately 20 volunteers took part in the clean-up and restoration activities in addition to 15 children from Dr. Maria Montessori Elementary School in Burgas, their teachers and parents. Three employees from the nearby Peugeot car service also offered their support and expressed a long-term interest in helping maintain the trail.

“Without the help of volunteers, it wouldn’t be possible to carry out all this work. Thanks to this action, we’re now able to open the season and welcome visitors to both the Trail and the Hide.”
 — *Mariya Andreeva*, Regional Inspectorate of Environment and Water – Burgas.

The Municipality of Burgas provided excellent support for the event by donating sanitary cleaning supplies and arranging for the waste to be removed the very next day, reinforcing the value of strong partnerships between local authorities and civil society for nature conservation.

Ocean Literacy Activity 4 – Biodiversity Carnival 2024: ‘Burgas on Three Lakes’

May 2024

The Biodiversity Carnival 2024, held as part of Burgas' Green Weekend (17–19 May), brought colour, creativity, and community spirit to the city streets. This beloved annual event celebrates biodiversity through a festive children's procession and costume competition.

This year's carnival theme, "Burgas on Three Lakes," aligned perfectly with the EmpowerUs pilot project of the same name, drawing attention to the city's rich natural heritage and promoting local environmental efforts. Approximately 160 children aged 3 to 10 from kindergartens and elementary schools across Burgas prepared costumes inspired by biodiversity, ranging from animals and plants to entire ecosystems. Many of the costumes were created using recycled materials, encouraging sustainability alongside creativity.

The event began with a lively procession from Burgas Municipality Square to the Sea Garden, where the participants showcased their creations on the open-air stage "The Snail." Each group presented their school or kindergarten, followed by an awards ceremony judged by a panel from the organising institutions. Award categories included: Best Animal Costume; Best Plant Costume; Best Flamingo; Best Recycled Materials Costume; Best Group Presentation; and Best Kindergarten/School Entry.

The event was co-organised by the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation, the Regional Inspectorate of Environment and Water – Burgas, and the Municipality of Burgas. It was attended by a diverse audience of families, educators, citizens, and officials, including the Mayor of Burgas and three Deputy Mayors (Culture, Education, and Ecology), marking a significant moment of public recognition for the initiative.

"This has always been an incredibly popular event for us but it's the first time that we've gotten such public recognition for it and for our work by the Mayor of Burgas. His appearance at the opening of the Biodiversity Carnival was a complete surprise for us, but it shows that the event has significance not only for us" – Radostina Tzenova, Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation, main organiser.

While the carnival was well-attended and smoothly organised, one notable challenge was its proximity to May 24th, Bulgaria's National Day of Culture and Literacy, a major school celebration that may have slightly reduced school participation compared to previous years. Nevertheless, the event succeeded in raising awareness of Burgas' biodiversity, promoting the "Burgas on Three Lakes" EmpowerUs pilot, and reinforcing the role of children and education in shaping a more sustainable future.

Ocean Literacy Activity 5 – A Day at Atanasovsko Lake: Burgas on Three Lakes

May 2024

As part of the Green Weekend in Burgas (17–19 May), a special ocean literacy event titled "A Day at Atanasovsko Lake" invited locals and visitors alike to explore and experience the unique biodiversity of this important coastal lagoon. The event was organised by the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation, in collaboration with the Regional Inspectorate of Environment and Water – Burgas and the Municipality of Burgas. Hosted along the scenic Avocet Trail and at the Birdwatching Hide, the event offered a full day of nature-based activities designed to engage people of all ages and raise awareness about the "Burgas on Three Lakes" pilot project under EmpowerUs.

Highlights of the day included:

- Four thematic lectures focused on the unique characteristics of Atanasovsko Lake, the richness of its birdlife, and the functioning of coastal lagoon ecosystems. These talks were paired with a guided nature walk along the Avocet Trail.
- All-day birdwatching, with high-quality binoculars and spotting scopes set up to provide visitors with the opportunity to observe a wide variety of bird species and their feeding behaviours up close.
- Two outdoor yoga classes, offering participants the chance to connect with nature and experience the calming and restorative atmosphere of the lagoon.

The event attracted a diverse audience, including schoolchildren (ages 5–18), families with children, local residents, birdwatching enthusiasts, and tourists visiting Burgas. Many families attended together, with parents and grandparents bringing children to learn about and enjoy the natural beauty of the lagoon. The combination of education, hands-on experience, and wellness activities helped foster a deeper appreciation for Atanasovsko Lake and its role in the region’s natural and cultural identity.

This successful event strengthened the visibility of the EmpowerUs Bulgarian pilot initiative and reinforced the importance of preserving urban coastal wetlands for both biodiversity and public well-being.

Ocean Literacy Activity 6 – Twilight Tales: Nocturnal Wildlife in the City (City Explorers event #2)

May 2024

As part of the Green Weekend in Burgas (17–19 May), the second event in the *City Explorers* series invited curious citizens to experience the mysterious world of nocturnal wildlife at Atanasovsko Lake. Titled ‘Twilight Tales’, the event took place at the Birdwatching Hide along the Avocet Trail and the surrounding area of Atanasovsko Lake and was designed

as a guided night expedition to awaken interest across all age groups in the rich and often unseen biodiversity of the area after dark.

Leading the exploration was Stanimira Deleva, a specialist in bats and dragonflies, who captivated participants with her expertise. Using specialised equipment—traps, cameras, and acoustic monitoring tools—she revealed the hidden nightlife of the lake, including bats, nocturnal insects, and bird species. Throughout the evening, she responded to a stream of questions from the eager audience, turning the experience into a hands-on, open-air classroom.

The group of 30 participants represented a wide cross-section of the community: families with children, teachers, university students, and older nature enthusiasts. Some participants had already taken part in the first *City Explorers* citizen science event, helping to form a small but growing community of urban nature lovers who actively engage with the EmpowerUs Bulgarian pilot.

“Do you think we will be able to see Eagle-owl during the walk?” asked one younger participant who was deeply inspired by the night life and amazing nocturnal species of the local biodiversity.

Despite strong interest, the TCL team noted that scheduling the event on a Saturday night, which coincided with the popular local *Night of Museums* in Burgas, may have limited attendance. Future editions might consider alternative timing to allow more people to join.

Twilight Tales successfully brought people together around a shared curiosity for the natural world, offering a rare glimpse into the magical biodiversity that thrives in the city’s coastal lagoon after sunset.

Ocean Literacy Activity 7 – Birthday Celebrations at Atanasovsko Lake Reserve

August 2024

On the 12th of August, Atanasovsko Lake marked 44 years since its designation as a nature reserve, and for over two decades the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation (BBF) and the Regional Inspectorate for Environment and Water – Burgas (RIEW) have celebrated the occasion with public events. This year’s festivities had ocean literacy at the core of the celebrations, with the day rich in art, music and nature experiences which participants enjoyed immensely.

This year, the celebration included the special art exhibition titled ‘Through the Dunes’, featuring captivating paintings of the local fauna and flora of the Burgas sand dunes and the various birds of Atanasovsko Lake by the young artist Polina Stoyanova. Polina, who has worked with BBF on dune conservation, was inspired by the lake during her visit during Green Weekend in Burgas and created the artwork especially for this event.

Polina is a visual artist working in illustration, animation, multimedia, and murals. She also facilitates sustainability-focused educational programs using the Non-formal Learning Methodology under the Erasmus+ programme.

“I’m very interested in the possibility of conveying important messages related to our surrounding nature and biodiversity, through the means of the visual. In the series of paintings dedicated to the flora and fauna of the Black Sea dunes, I’m trying to convey the beauty and variety of colours and shapes that thrive in them. The delicate and gentle inhabitants of the dunes deserve our attention and admiration and most of all - they deserve to continue to exist” – Polina Stoyanova.

Visitors enjoyed birdwatching through telescopes and binoculars, educational games for children, and a stand with products with a cause supporting local conservation efforts. Guests were treated to a beautifully decorated cake adorned with the lake’s most charismatic inhabitant: the pink flamingo.

A major highlight of the day was the announcement of a milestone for the reserve; the first ever successful breeding of the Greater Flamingo at Atanasovsko Lake, including the hatching of three

chicks. This hatching of the chicks is a sign that Atanasovsko Lake is now perceived by the birds as a safe home, after eight years of inhabiting the area but never raising chicks there. The news drew wide interest, including from journalists and nature conservation partners.

Approximately 50 people attended the event, including representatives from BBF, RIEW, Strandja Nature Park, the Poda Center, and members of the public. Notably, the event attracted many first-time visitors to the lake, highlighting a growing interest in the lake and creating new connections between the TCL team and the citizens of Burgas.

Ocean Literacy Activity 8 – Who created the new logo of Atanasovsko Lake?

October 2024

An ocean literacy event took place at the Birdwatching Hide along the shores of Atanasovsko Lake in Burgas to unveil and celebrate the new logo of the lake. The event was the culmination of a creative competition held among third- and fourth-year students majoring in “Poster and Visual Communication” at the National Academy of Arts (NAA) in Sofia and its Burgas Branch during the 2023/2024 academic year.

More than 40 original proposals were submitted, each offering a unique artistic interpretation of Atanasovsko Lake, its salt pans, rich biodiversity, and iconic birdlife. The EmpowerUs project selection committee had a difficult task but ultimately chose the work of Ina Vezenkova as the winning design. Her logo beautifully captured the lake's vibrant seasonal colours, from the pink crystallisation ponds used for sea salt extraction to the green-blue waters teeming with life. Birds wading, swimming, and soaring feature prominently in her design, symbolising the lake's vital role as a habitat for the 334 bird species.

In addition to the award ceremony, the winning and shortlisted logos were exhibited in front of the Hide, allowing the public to view and vote for their favourites. The event also included birdwatching sessions at the lake and a cocktail gathering to celebrate the creativity and enthusiasm of the students.

Over 40 people attended, including the competition winners, representatives from the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation (BBF), EmpowerUs, the National Academy of Arts, the Municipality of Burgas, the Regional Inspectorate of Environment and Water (RIEW) Burgas, members of the media, and lake enthusiasts.

The newly selected logo will now serve as the official visual identity for Atanasovsko Lake and will be used to promote the area as a protected coastal lagoon of international importance, home to the country's only sea salt production site, a source of healing mud and saltwater, and the richest bird habitat in Bulgaria.

“Our work with the students was very successful thanks to our partnership with BBF. It was made possible with the help of Bilyana Desheva, a former student who fell in love with Atanasovsko Lake and BBF’s mission” – Assoc. Prof. Nenko Atanasov, National Academy of Arts.

Ocean Literacy Activity 9 – Climate evolution: Are we ready for the new climate?

December 2024

An engaging and educational day-long ocean literacy event was hosted at the Flora Burgas Expo Center exploring climate change and our readiness for its growing impact. More than 70 participants, including students, educators, and concerned citizens, joined a dynamic and diverse programme blending science, music, and activism.

The event opened with a keynote presentation by Radostina Tzenova from the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation (BBF), titled *“Climate Change – Are We Ready for the New Climate?”*. She addressed the pressing climate challenges facing Bulgaria and the world and emphasised how young people, in particular, can equip themselves with knowledge and skills to adapt and respond effectively to these new realities.

One of the event highlights was the Climate Fresk workshop—an innovative, science-based game that helps participants quickly understand the complex causes and consequences of climate change. Facilitated by Bozhil Kondev, Blagovesta Popova-Petkova, and Krasimira Gavriloova, five teams explored the IPCC science in a hands-on, visual, and collaborative way, creating their own “fresks” to illustrate climate processes and solutions.

Vasil Aleksiev from the Bulgarian Red Cross shared real-life experiences from his fieldwork, highlighting various types of climate-related disasters and offering practical advice for emergency preparedness in his talk on *“Climate Disaster Education.”*

Throughout the day, musical performances by talented young artists added inspiration and energy. Audiences enjoyed the sounds of Aglaya Todorova and her guitarist, Kamen Petrov, and the impressive 12-year-old guitarist Iskren Todorov, whose music created a thoughtful and vibrant atmosphere.

The afternoon sessions focused on climate action through cycling. Radostina Tzenova and Mariana Sarbova introduced *‘Burgas on Three Lakes and One Sea’*, the EmpowerUs Bulgarian pilot that is exploring cycling opportunities around the city’s coastal and lake areas. They shared how areas like Atanasovsko Lake have become popular for cycling, while other coastal areas remain underutilised, despite their potential for enhancing nature-connectedness and ocean literacy.

Radost Marina from Velo Evolution, Sofia, presented “FOR” more cyclists, exploring solutions and standards for safe and comfortable cycling. Her talk sparked a lively discussion with the audience on

the current state and future potential of Burgas' cycling network. The event concluded with an inspiring talk by Svetoslav Mitev: *"From Lisbon to Malaga: 1500 km of Bike Parking."* His story sparked curiosity and set the stage for more initiatives focused on sustainable mobility and climate resilience by the coast of Burgas.

Organised by the *Greenburg+* project (Erasmus+), with support from EmpowerUs and the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation, the event successfully brought together climate and ocean literacy, community dialogue, and creative expression in a city that sits on the frontlines of climate change. The event was also very successful in engaging and inspiring young people, a group who currently lack enough information about these topics in Burgas.

"This is one of my dreams—to organise events like this for the young people of Burgas. They are in a difficult position: vulnerable because they live by the sea, yet not sufficiently informed or prepared for the realities of the changing climate" – Radostina Tzenova, BBF.

Ocean Literacy Activity 10 – Lagoon Clean Jamboree 2025

April 2025

A second Lagoon Clean Jamboree was organised under the EmpowerUs project to bring together passionate volunteers, local institutions, and community partners for a day of action and restoration at Atanasovsko Lake, preparing the Avocet Trail for the upcoming summer tourism season.

One of the major highlights was the incredible contribution of the SFA RETAIL BURGAS team, who, entirely at their own initiative and expense, constructed a brand-new screen installation. This structure will soon serve as an open-air educational and exhibition space, offering artists and educators a unique platform to present their work in harmony with the lake's natural setting.

Volunteers from the Regional Inspectorate for Environment and Water – Burgas (RIEW Burgas) joined the effort, contributing to essential maintenance activities along the trail. The SFA team also handled the mowing of overgrown vegetation, while other volunteers helped clean and organise the Bird Observatory.

Illegal fire remnants were cleared, old wood was removed, and the entire area was refreshed, ready to welcome curious visitors, nature lovers, and school groups.

The 2025 cleanup comes at a pivotal moment, in preparation for the Avocet Trail receiving a full renovation as part of the 'Burgas of Three Lakes and One Sea' pilot initiative, which includes a new outdoor classroom, an educational trail for young visitors, updated information boards, observation points and scenic lookouts, bicycle parking and a number of other small but impactful improvements to enrich the lake experience and further engage in ocean literacy for all.

Around 30 participants, including citizens of Burgas, the RIEW Burgas team, and the dedicated staff of SFA RETAIL BURGAS, contributed their time, energy, and goodwill to make the day a resounding success.

“The support from SFA RETAIL BURGAS is truly special for us. These men organise everything themselves including materials, labour, and logistics—and the positive impacts are visible straight away. This year, we were also happily surprised by the large group from RIEW Burgas, especially their director, who worked tirelessly throughout the day.” — Diana Pavlova, Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation.

The Lagoon Clean Jamboree continues to grow as a model for community-driven conservation and ocean literacy efforts, where civic pride, corporate responsibility, and environmental stewardship come together by the shores of Burgas.

Ocean Literacy Activity 11 – Biodiversity Carnival 2025: ‘Burgas on Three Lakes and One Sea’ **May 2025**

The Biodiversity Carnival 2025, co-organised by the TCL team, took place at the Municipality Square of Burgas and the Sea Garden’s Culture Centre ‘Sea Casino’. The event was attended by approximately 270 children from various kindergartens in Burgas, their teachers, parents, and grandparents. It was organised by the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation in partnership with the Municipality of Burgas and the Regional Inspectorate of Environment and Water (RIEW) Burgas. This year, the Institute of Oceanology at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IoO BAS) supported the carnival, providing Black Sea-themed books for all children and joining the jury alongside Anna Antonova from EmpowerUs and a RIEW representative.

The carnival’s theme, ‘Burgas on Three Lakes and One Sea’, highlighted the EmpowerUs Bulgarian pilot and its vision for the future. Through this platform, the TCL team promoted awareness of the local ecosystems, engaging children and their teachers and families deeply in learning about the lakes and the sea’s inhabitants.

The strong partnership between organisers was key to the event’s success. The Municipality invited participants and provided the venue and technical equipment free of charge, while RIEW and IoO BAS contributed awards for the participants. Bulgarian National Television broadcasted the parade and carnival opening live, greatly increasing public reach and awareness.

Ocean Literacy Activity 12 – Green Day: Actions for the Burgas Dune

May 2025

As part of Green Weekend 2025 in Burgas, the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation organised a hands-on conservation initiative to protect the Burgas Dune. Despite a rainy morning and the risk of postponement, the event went ahead, powered by the commitment of over 50 enthusiastic volunteers.

The main focus of the activity was the installation of a light protective fence along nearly 800 metres of the dune area. The goal was to guide visitors along established paths and prevent unintentional trampling, helping to preserve the dune's fragile ecosystem and the rare species it supports. The event was carried out in close coordination with the Regional Inspectorate of Environment and Water – Burgas, ensuring that all activities aligned with local environmental regulations.

Approximately 50 volunteers were actively involved in every step of the fence installation, including cutting and sharpening wooden pegs, attaching hooks, threading and tensioning four-metre-long ropes, working efficiently in good spirits. A key partner involved in the efforts was the UniCredit Bank, with members of staff from the Burgas branch volunteering to help, strengthening ties between the private sector and civil society. The team of volunteers managed to complete the entire stretch in just two hours, helped by a break in the weather and excellent group coordination. To further support public education and outreach, two informational signs were installed at the main entrances to the dune. These were constructed to provide visitors with important facts about the dune habitat, its ecological value, and guidelines for respectful access.

Key outcomes include the installation of the protective fencing, the placement of the educational signs at key dune access points, 50 participants engaged in dune conservation, and increased public awareness of the ecological importance of coastal dune systems. As a result of the engaging ocean literacy event, the Burgas Dune will be better prepared for the busy summer months, thanks to the collective effort of local businesses, families, and conservation professionals, all working together to protect one of Burgas' most unique natural treasures.

Ocean Literacy Activity 13 – Launch of the Renovated Avocet Trail

September 2025

As part of the Bulgaria TCL pilot final event, the newly renovated Avocet Trail was launched, where attendees were introduced to the new elements of the trail, including new educational signs, places for rest and bird watching observation points. The Avocet Trail welcomed the institutions, organisations, and companies that have previously helped maintain the Trail and on whom the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation rely to continue supporting them in the future, as the trail is mainly a product of the shared care and collaboration of various people who have an interest in preserving and developing the lake in the best possible way.

The municipality have also been great supporters of the renovation and are looking to provide and install a 5G camera on the roof of the birdwatching hide to provide a 24/7 view of life at Atanasovsko Lake. The Mayor of Burgas has also personally endorsed and promoted the trail.

4.3 Eastern Limassol Region, Cyprus

Ocean Literacy Activity 1 – Getting to Know My Coastline

November 2023

In an effort to foster a sense of environmental stewardship among the younger generations in the Eastern Limassol Region, an engaging and educational ocean literacy event, 'Getting to Know My Coastline', was organised for students and staff from the local primary school, 'Ayioi Anargyroi Moni-Monagrouli'. Through this ocean literacy activity, the TCL team (comprised of the Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute (CMMI) and the Development Agency of Limassol) wanted to establish meaningful connections with the younger population living in the Eastern Limassol Region, in addition to introducing the 70 school children and their teachers to the ecological richness of their local coastline, and creating a shared feeling of pride towards their coastal community.

The day began with a beach clean-up event at the Moni beach, introducing school children and staff to the importance of the sand dunes and the beach rock present in the area. The group then visited the newly designated Marine Protected Area (MPA) of Ayios Georgios Alamanos, which hosts a mosaic of marine habitats and acts as an important resting place for the endangered Mediterranean Monk Seal. Officers from the Department of Fisheries and Marine Research, Melina Marcou & Yiannis Ioannou, joined the group during the excursion and provided insights about how the area requires further protection, and what the students and teachers can do to help. The day ended at the Cyprus Institute's PROTEAS research facility where students and teachers were given a tour and were informed about the important research conducted on renewable energies.

The ocean literacy event was a great success and allowed the local primary school children connect to and learn more about their local coastal environment in Eastern Limassol.

Ocean Literacy Activity 2 – Here Only Monachus Workshops

November 2024

Interactive workshops were held for students in two local primary schools in the Eastern Limassol Region to connect children with the local marine life, in particular the endangered Mediterranean monk seal. The activity, called 'Here Only Monachus', engaged approximately 80 students in marine topics using artistic approaches, including original recordings of natural seal sounds. Following interactive presentations about the local marine life, the students were asked to create postcards and banners with their own messages for both the monk seal and the sea. This hands-on approach was designed to inspire environmental literacy and awareness of marine ecosystems, with the children expressing their learnings and feelings about the ocean through art.

The workshops were facilitated by local educator, Rebecca Katsaris, while professional artist, Chloe Finn, supported the students to draw creatures living in the marine environment.

The activity encouraged the students to increase their awareness about the local marine environment and allowed them to discuss and reflect on the importance of marine conservation, in addition to their emotional connections to the ocean. Reflecting on the event, Maria Hadjimichael, Academic Lead from CMMI, shared that hands-on activities like 'Here Only Monachus' in which children get the opportunity to create their own artwork are effective initiatives to engage younger audiences and to make abstract ocean-related concepts more relatable and memorable for them.

The 'Here Only Monachus' creative workshop forms part of the activities of the educational project 'Increasing Marine Environmental Awareness Through the Creative Arts' that Rebecca Katsaris has been leading since 2022, with the support of the [Cyprus Environment Foundation](#) and [Enalia Physis Environmental Research Centre](#). It is officially endorsed by [Mission Ocean](#) and [BlueMissionMed](#).

4.4 Åland Islands, Finland

Ocean Literacy Activity 1 – Seminar and Field Visit: Importance of Dikes and Waterways on Åland March 2025

This Ocean Literacy activity highlighted the crucial role that inland waterways and dikes on Åland play as natural spawning grounds for the iconic sea trout (*Salmo trutta*). The aim of the activity was to raise awareness of the need for more nature-inclusive management of these habitats and to illustrate how actions taken several kilometres inland can have a direct impact on fish stocks in the surrounding marine environment.

To support this, Swedish field biologist Dan Calderon was invited to Åland to lead an interactive programme of seminars and field visits focused on these issues. Dan has many years of hands-on restoration experience and an in-depth understanding of the challenges faced by land-use sectors such as agriculture and forestry. His expertise helped bridge the gap between ecological theory and practical, stakeholder-informed action. The target audience for this initiative included local land and water owners, farmers, forestry professionals, excavator operators, fish conservationists, and local government representatives. Over the course of 2.5 days, all these target groups were successfully engaged through a mix of seminars and field visits.

Day 1 focused on field visits with local government and the NGO Ålands Fiskevårdsförening, identifying sites with high potential for trout habitat restoration in the short-term. Days 2 and 3 included a stakeholder seminar with 35 participants and a field visit attended by 25 individuals. All stakeholder groups were represented across both activities.

The event was co-organised by EmpowerUs and the project [Smarta Vatten](#) (Smart Waters), a natural collaboration given Smarta Vatten's established work with farmers on water management in the landscape. A concrete outcome of the activity was the restocking of approximately 21,000 smolt of sea trout into identified, environmentally healthy waterways that could become potential spawning grounds for trout. This was a collaborative effort between the local fisheries conservation NGO, local government, and landowners and water owners alike. One of the key lessons from this initiative was the importance of trust between experts proposing ecological measures and the local communities expected to carry them out. Dan Calderon's practical experience and ability to communicate in relatable terms proved vital in building this trust. While some conflicts of interest remain between

nature conservation goals and land-use practices, framing the discussion around an iconic migratory fish species like sea trout helped foster a valuable dialogue between land and sea perspectives.

Recommendations for future improvements include organising additional field visits to showcase a wider variety of restoration examples and scheduling activities during peak fish migration or monitoring periods. This would allow participants to witness sea trout in action, even in small, improbable water bodies, thereby deepening engagement and understanding of marine life and fish behaviour.

Ocean Literacy Activity 2 – National Fishing Day

May 2025

The National Day of Fishing is a nation-wide event aimed at promoting fisheries and sparks interest primarily among children in fish, fishing culture and aquatic life in general. The Åland TCL team collaborated on an ocean literacy event hosted primarily by the local 4H-Club which has a fisheries network for children, in collaboration with Lokalkraft Leader Åland. The event took place on the harbour docks at the Port of Mariehamn, where participants could borrow and learn to use fishing rods to fish for herring. The EmpowerUs team helped the participants humanly dispose of the fish and clean what they caught. The team also brought cooking equipment to cook the herring for participants. Additionally, the team put together a quiz about local fish species and provided insightful information about the different fish, where to find them and what we need to do in order to protect the stocks and have healthy populations.

“Oh look, you caught half a bucket of herring! Now you get to eat it all week. Did you know a lot of other species also eat herring?” – Viktor Eriksson, Government of Åland.

“This perch is over 20cm so it’s good to keep, any smaller and you should put it back. There are minimum requirements on most fish species to keep the populations healthy!” – Linda Sundström, Government of Åland.

A total of 130 visitors attended the event, with children and youth making up approximately half of the attendees. A positive outcome of the activity was that a lot of children who might not have a direct tie to the ocean had the opportunity to try fishing for the first time and learn more about different fish species and the current state of our oceans. It was also one of the few activities that the Åland TCL team EmpowerUs got to engage with families, children and youth on a deeper level. In relation to

youth participation, it was very valuable to join forces with an established partner who is experienced in engaging with children and youth (i.e. 4H-Club) for the event. The practical elements of the event such as the fishing and the cooking facilitated in keeping the children and families engaged throughout the day.

Ocean Literacy Activity 3 – Åland Water Stewardship Campaign and Seminar

May 2025

This Ocean Literacy activity aimed to activate and support the large water-owning community on Åland. This was done firstly by running a water ownership campaign and sending out a leaflet about water ownership to the residents of Åland. The leaflet included information on how to check if you own water on Åland and your rights and obligations as a water owner. The TCL team also included useful information on the leaflet about where you can find funding for projects that benefit the ocean and information about what we can do to stop the most destructive actions in shallow water areas which are some of the most productive and biodiverse but also were almost everything is within the realm of private ownership since hundreds of years. As a follow-up to the campaign, a Water Ownership seminar was organised as a means to provide additional information and guidance on water ownership and stewardship on Åland, as well as to present findings from EmpowerUs and the results of a survey about water commons that was performed in 2024, highlighting different topics on fish conservation, fisheries, challenges and needs.

The target audience was primarily water owners on Åland but the TCL partners also wanted to reach others who are interested in the waters surrounding Åland, like coastal residents, second home owners and recreational fishers for example. Therefore, the leaflet was sent out to all 15,700 registered households on Åland. As a follow-up to the campaign, a seminar was organised to provide people with additional information and guidance on water ownership and stewardship on Åland. The seminar was advertised to local water owners but also others with an interest in our coastal waters were invited to join.

The seminar had 50 participants, 40 in person and 10 online. A vast majority were water owners and people who had not been reached previously in the EmpowerUs project. The audience were mainly men, which is something that the TCL team have regularly noticed throughout EmpowerUs when it comes to fisheries and water management, but a small number of women and youth also attended.

The outcomes of the activity were that parts of the water owning community came together in a new forum. As a part of the campaign, a [resource website](#) was also created. This website provides useful resources for those who want to get involved in water stewardship on Åland, including a template for a fisheries management plan, a checklist for successful conservation projects and various knowledge tools, both the Ålandic government's own tools but also links to tools produced by others in the area. The Ålandic online tools have gotten new layouts and have also been edited for machine reading to make them more accessible for people with disabilities.

The public response to the campaign and seminar has been positive and it has sparked a broader interest from the Ålandic community in responsible water ownership and has strengthened the connection between the government and the general public.

To communicate on these topics with such a broad stakeholder group is not easy as people have very different views. What one group might see as exploitation of common natural resources another group see as a sustainable harvest. To make room for the different views is very important. Scientists also disagree so one must be mindful in order to get as broad a view as possible. One must also be considerate about time. People don't manage their, often inherited, waters as a professional occupation so there is always a trade-off with other obligations and life in general. Likewise, the geographical distance on Åland is considerable in the archipelago so to host seminars as hybrid events is critical to ensure a fair chance of participation, also to vary venues geographically. The TCL have also struggled to engage women and youth. Even though all groups were represented at the seminar, it has proven difficult throughout EmpowerUs to engage with these groups, so a reflection on what forums are suitable for different groups of people is important going forward when running similar ocean literacy initiatives.

Ocean Literacy Activity 4 – Exhibition: The Living Cultural Heritage of Traditional Herring Fishing on Åland

May 2025 onwards

Traditional herring fishing with gill nets is one of the most important expressions of Åland's coastal culture and heritage. For centuries, it has shaped local livelihoods, language, boat building, shore construction, handicrafts, and even ownership practices of land and sea. Today, this practice remains protected by law, ensuring that every resident of Åland retains the right to fish for herring with gill nets, regardless of private ownership of waters, a testament to its historic role as a vital means of survival.

To safeguard and share this heritage, EmpowerUs partnered with the Museum of Hunting and Fishing in Eckerö to renew the museum's display and launch the new Herring Fishing exhibition. The work was enriched by structured interviews with fishers who are still commercially active, capturing their knowledge and perspectives. These oral histories have been archived at Åbo Akademi University's ethnological archives, ensuring they are preserved for future research.

The exhibition illustrates how herring fishing has remained remarkably consistent for hundreds of years, while also highlighting the ecological significance of Baltic herring as a keystone species in the marine ecosystem. Visitors are introduced to both the cultural and environmental dimensions of this tradition, as well as the threats facing herring populations today, such as eutrophication and climate change.

The exhibition is designed for a wide range of visitors, including tourists, local schools, policymakers, government officials, and fisheries stakeholders. With around 10,000 visitors annually, the museum provides a powerful platform to make the intangible cultural heritage of herring fishing in Åland more visible and accessible. By showing how certain fishing practices are sustainable and deeply embedded in coastal identity, the exhibition helps nuance perceptions of commercial fishing and informs discussions about biodiversity protection.

This Ocean Literacy activity underscores the importance of distinguishing between destructive and sustainable marine practices when designing fair and effective biodiversity protections. It offers evidence and insights into a traditional, community-rooted way of using the sea responsibly.

One key lesson was that creating an engaging and interactive exhibition for audiences without prior interest in the topic is challenging. With more time and resources, greater emphasis could have been placed on interactive elements to enhance accessibility and enjoyment for all visitors.

4.5 Connemara and the Aran Islands, Ireland

Ocean Literacy Activity 1 – Marine Identities Workshop

May 2025

In collaboration with the Irish Ocean Literacy Network (IOLN), the Irish TCL team organised a Marine Identities workshop in Lettermullan, Connemara. The event formed part of a wider series of IOLN regional meetings, an ongoing initiative by IOLN that regularly brings together ocean champions to spark collaboration on ocean literacy initiatives across the island of Ireland. The event was attended by approximately 25 people including local representatives from Lettermullan and South Connemara, eight local secondary school students and a number of members of IOLN. The workshop sought to enable discussion and dialogue on the concept of Marine Identity.

Marine Identity reflects a deep connection with the ocean and influences how a person understands and experiences the ocean. It refers to the ways in which the ocean is entwined with our sense of self, including our thoughts, feelings, emotions, values, and behaviours. In other words, it is the answer to the questions, ‘Who am I?’ and ‘How does the ocean shape who I am?’ By exploring Marine Identity, we can better understand why individuals perceive their connection with the ocean in a particular way and how the impacts of coastal change are experienced by different people. The concept of Marine Identity can also be used to empower people to protect the ocean and encourage decision-makers to actively consider the relationships that people have with the sea.

The workshop enabled discussion through a combination of formal presentations from professionals working in the marine sector as well as by providing an open forum for workshop participants to share their reflections on marine identity and provided opportunities for participants to illustrate their connection to the ocean through visual storytelling. Participants were invited to bring objects or photographs to the workshop that formed part of their ocean story or prompted memories and experiences of the ocean.

The programme for the day also included a visit to the Lettermullan and Gorumna Heritage Centre, which showcases the personal collection of John Bhaba Jeaic Ó Conghaile, who has been collecting historical artifacts from the local area and across Ireland for decades. John Bhaba Jeaic was also the first speaker of the day, discussing his personal reflections on the marine heritage of the local area.

The event also featured a sean-nós song from Stiofán, an employee of the Heritage Centre. Sean-nós (old style) singing is unaccompanied, traditional Irish vocal music usually performed in the Irish language.

In preparation for the workshop, an outline of the methodology was created by Lindsey West, which could be adapted and used by others as a resource for future similar Ocean Literacy activities. By engaging with the Irish Ocean Literacy Network, the workshop helped to broaden the engagement of the EmpowerUs project and the Irish TCL and provided opportunities for potential future collaboration.

By having secondary school students attend, the EmpowerUs project's Irish TCL expanded its engagement with young people, who were not previously engaged with the TCL's pilot work. One of the main takeaways from the activity was the value of collaborating with different organisations in the planning of the event. Without the support of Údarás na Gaeltachta and the network of the IOLN, the workshop would not have been as well attended otherwise.

One challenge was the language dimension – as the event was held primarily in the Irish language, attendees who were not fluent Irish speakers were limited in their ability to engage in discussion. Holding the event in Irish was appropriate given the location of the event and the partnership with Údarás na Gaeltachta, but more efforts for translation or bilingual discussion would have supported engagement for other attendees.

“The communities along Connemara’s coastline have a deep and intimate relationship with the ocean. This workshop was a fascinating glimpse into the connections between local people and the sea. By using the concept of marine identity, we can get exposure to the complex interrelationship between place attachment, heritage, the environment, and identity” – Alex Miller, Queen’s University Belfast.

Overall, the workshop was very successful and has sparked an interest by others in running similar initiatives across Ireland. The workshop also received media attention, with coverage of the event on [RTÉ Raidió na Gaeltachta](#), the national radio station in Ireland, broadcasting in Irish.

Ocean Literacy Activity 2 – Webinar on Reflections of Marine Identities

June 2025

This webinar was organised by the Irish TCL team in collaboration with the Irish Ocean Literacy Network and served as a follow-up ocean literacy event to share the findings from the Marine Identities workshop held in Lettermullan. The online event sought to examine the connections between Ocean Literacy and Marine Identity through discussion of these concepts and reflections on the previous Marine Identities workshop. The webinar included an introduction by Catherine McCann (Executive Officer at the Irish Ocean Literacy Network) and presentations by Dr Lindsey West and Alex Miller (Queen’s University Belfast) on the topics of Marine Identity and Ocean Literacy. The presentations included reflections on the Marine Identities workshop held in Lettermullan and recommendations for participants interested in adapting these concepts for their own activities. The presentations were followed by an open Q&A / discussion session where audience members asked questions and shared reflections on the topic from their own experiences.

The target audience for the webinar was community organisers, activists, and people with an interest in ocean literacy. The event was advertised through the EmpowerUs website and social media and disseminated by the Irish Ocean Literacy Network to their members. The bulk of attendees appeared to have a connection to the Irish Ocean Literacy Network. 44 people registered to attend the webinar, and 27 people attended. Participants were primarily based in Ireland but included audience members joining from Bangladesh, France, the UK, and the United States.

The conversations sparked during this webinar clearly showed that marine identity resonates deeply with people across Ireland and beyond. By bringing together diverse voices and experiences, marine identity can contribute toward more inclusive and place-based approaches to ocean literacy and stewardship. The webinar was recorded and is available to watch publicly on the IOLN YouTube channel [here](#).

4.6 Træna, Norway

Ocean Literacy Activity 1 – Hekta på Træna (Hooked on Træna)

July 2024

As part of Trænafestivalen 2024, an annual summer festival held on Træna, the Norwegian TCL team co-organised a unique treasure hunt for festivalgoers, tourists and families alike. The event, called Hekta på Træna (Hooked on Træna in English), was organised to promote the strong cultural relationship between the Træna community and the sea, and to give participants a glimpse into the rich fishing history of the islands.

The objective of the event was to promote the ties between the Træna community and the sea to visitors outside of Træna, emphasising the key Ocean Literacy Principles that "the ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems" and "the ocean and humans are inextricably linked," and involved approximately 60 participants in a treasure hunt that featured ten posts spread across the main island. Each post along the treasure hunt featured various interactive activities and unique insights into Træna's rich maritime heritage and pressing environmental issues. Certain activities focused on the history of fishing and the cultural connections between the people of Træna and the sea, while others addressed the issue of ocean plastics through beach art and interactive games. At each post, participants answered questions about fishing objects, fish species, and ocean connections or took part in marine-themed activities. Stamps were collected at each post, culminating at the finish line, where participants enjoyed a complimentary fish barbecue.

This Ocean Literacy activity was an instrumental first step in the development of a permanent standalone cultural (hiking) trail on Træna, promoting the island municipality's cultural heritage and nature-connectedness, as detailed in Norway's Ocean Literacy Activity 3 below. The Hooked on Træna trail initiative aims to foster a wider recognition of the connections between the Træna community and the sea, ultimately contributing to a broader societal understanding and appreciation for the ocean within and beyond Træna.

Ocean Literacy Activity 2 – ‘Matauk’ Seminar at Træna Winter Festival: Take Træna by Storm

February 2025

The Norwegian TCL team arranged an ocean literacy seminar at the annual Træna Winter Festival under the theme ‘Matauk’, a Norwegian term used to describe the harvesting of food resources found in nature, in addition to what is grown or purchased. The event involved cross-TCL collaboration, whereby members of the Finnish TCL team, Kristina Svells (Academic Lead, LUKE) and Viktor Eriksson (Local Host, Government of Åland) were invited to contribute to the seminar. Kristina talked about the local challenges that the community of Åland is experiencing, with many participants identifying parallels to the challenges along the Norwegian coast.

Viktor led a cooking demonstration and served herring, halibut and white bacalao to participants. During this cooking demonstration, Viktor discussed how, due to the fishing industry, herring is mainly valued only in terms of how much tonnage it makes up in fishmeal or as a by-product. For him, it’s important to reclaim the herring’s intrinsic value as good food and raw material for people for many generations. This message was conveyed by serving the festival guests dishes where herring was the central ingredient. The guests were overwhelmed with enthusiasm for how good it tasted – and many said that they gained a whole new perspective on herring as a raw material. Several participants were surprised at how good it tasted. They reflected on how they had grown up eating herring as children, but that it had rarely been a highlight for them, apart from Christmas herring and tomato herring, which many people are in the habit of eating.

The seminar was attended by 80 participants, including locals from Træna as well as visitors from other municipalities in Nordland. Few participants also came from further parts of Norway, including Bergen. The event also featured a screening of filmmaker Siri Hermansen’s film, ‘Freedom of the Sea’, which explores the impact of globalisation on the fishing industry and democratic rights, such as the common law right to the sea. Finally, a ‘Sofa Chat’ was hosted by EmpowerUs coordinator, Maiken Bjørkan, titled ‘The future of the ocean gap’, exploring the various current challenges, needs and opportunities for coastal communities. Maiken facilitated the conversation between, Kristina Svells, filmmaker Siri Hermansen, Sverre Hyttan (Manager of Pelagia Fish Factory, Træna), Mikael Forselius (Chairman of the Board of Ytri, the new hotel in Træna) and Helene Amundsen (local bachelor’s student).

The ocean literacy activity was a great opportunity for cross-TCL learning and highlighted the value of ocean literacy initiatives in connecting different research environments and local coastal communities

in different countries, fostering mutual learning and a deeper understanding of each community's unique relationship with the ocean.

Ocean Literacy Activity 3 – Our Blue Cultural Heritage: The Pole Hunt

Ongoing activity – Launched June 2025

This Ocean Literacy activity is an extension of the Hekta på Træna treasure hunt, the pilot Ocean Literacy activity that was carried out during the Træna Festival 2024. After the initial trial of the activity, there were ambitions to develop a more permanent legacy trail on the island of Træna, linking with digital tools and showcasing the rich culture and captivating stories of the community members, past and present.

After Træna Festival 2024, the Norway TCL team worked with the local community to develop a blue heritage trail that tells the story of the Sea People in Træna. The team worked together with residents of the four islands of Husøy, Selvær, Sanna and Sandøy, and collected 26 unique stories from as many places around the islands. The cultural heritage trail gives both residents and visitors the opportunity to learn about life in the coastal community and the sea itself. The goal is to show what it is like to live and work in Træna, and to provide insight into the people, stories and cultural heritage that have shaped this unique place over thousands of years.

In collaboration with the local population, the Polar Circle Outdoor Council, Mo Orienteering Club, and KPH, the cultural trail was adopted by a national orienteering app '[Stolpejakten](#)', where participants can freely sign up to 'collect' the orienteering posts, as the first example of a 'story trail' for the company.

The cultural trail was [announced prior to](#), and launched during, Trænafestivalen 2025, along with the Norwegian version of the Women Making Waves Booklet, and will be available all summer for participants to take part. The established Stolpejakten app will track the uptake of each story 'post' or 'pole'. If popular, the Stolpejakten will use the posts again in future years (another application for funds has been submitted, to replicate the model in a nearby fjord). The 'story template' will be made available to the community contributors to adapt and work with Stolpejakten in future years (through the 'Hekta på Træna Pilot Strategy', bringing together all the resources and tools from the pilot for future use). Some of the stories are being recreated with local artists as murals across the islands, funded by the EmpowerUs Pilot fund.

Initial feedback from Stolpejackten, that automatically evaluates the visitors to each post, has found the pole hunt to be very successful at engaging locals, as well as visitors. 246 new app registrations took place during the festival, 50 of which have connection to Træna; and almost 200 were outsiders learning about the *'havfolk'* connection with the sea. The pole hunt has been organised in Træna for the past 18 years. After the pilot in 2025, the figures show that the engagement has never been higher. In 2024, 299 people participated on 20 poles on Sanna and Husøy, of which 27 were local. In the first two months since its launch in 2025, the number has increased to 319 participants, distributed over 26 poles on Sanna, Husøy, Selvær and Sandøy, of which 60 are local, and there are two more months for people to join. Given the population of the islands is less than 500 residents, an update of over 12% is considered success.

4.7 Cap de Creus, Spain

Ocean Literacy Activity 1 – MarInfluencers

March 2024

The EmpowerUs Spain TCL team organised an engaging ocean literacy initiative called 'MarInfluencers' at a local high school in Roses, Catalonia. Aimed at educating and engaging approximately 40 high school students aged 16-17, this unique activity was designed to blend ocean stewardship and education with modern communication skills, empowering students to become advocates for ocean conservation.

The initiative was co-organised by the Sea Peoples Lab at Autonomous University of Barcelona (Academic Lead and Local Host) and BlueGreen Vision, an organisation aiming to reconnect humans with nature. The activity consisted of a series of three workshops, each building upon the last.

During the first workshop, titled 'Exploring the Ocean', students were introduced to key topics such as ocean biology, geology, physics and current environmental challenges, to gain a better understanding of marine ecosystems. The next workshop, titled 'The Voice of the Ocean', focused on science communication and outreach, teaching students on how to effectively use social media to raise awareness about ocean conservation issues. The final workshop, titled 'Ocean on Screen', encouraged students to showcase the marine conservation videos they created to their peers.

This hands-on initiative encouraged students to develop key skills in digital storytelling and advocacy. The activity also enhanced the students' knowledge on and interest in local and global marine issues, motivating them to become ambassadors for ocean conservation.

Ocean Literacy Activity 2 – Food Sovereignty Forum

October 2024

The Spain TCL team hosted an interactive event focused on highlighting sustainable practices in local food systems at the Cap de Creus Transition Coastal Lab in Spain. In collaboration with Inspira Gastronomía, the event gathered over 100 attendees, which included local experts, artisanal fishers, producers, activists, local authorities and enthusiastic members of the public.

The event facilitated discussions and activities that emphasised the interconnectedness of the local territory, the sea, and local food systems to foster a deeper understanding of sustainable practices. The aim of the event was to promote the concept of food sovereignty as an enabler of ocean literacy, focusing on the right of local communities to define their food, fisheries, and agricultural policies while ensuring sustainable access and use of marine and coastal resources.

The event featured various roundtable discussions as well as a live cooking demonstration that promoted local blue and green foods. A key achievement of the event was during the roundtable on sustainable fishing and aquaculture, where the importance of artisanal fishing was recognised in preserving local marine ecosystems and strengthening local food sovereignty in Cap de Creus. The roundtable discussion also emphasised the sea as a vital resource for Cap de Creus, highlighting the fundamental connections between the land and the sea and empowering participants to advocate for more targeted regulations and sustainable practices.

Reflecting on the event, the Spanish TCL team from the Autonomous University of Barcelona highlighted the importance of ensuring effective collaboration between different sectors, particularly agriculture and fisheries to address sustainability goals. The team hopes that the new Cap de Creus Forum, established as part of the EmpowerUs project, can act as a vehicle to ignite further collaboration and enhance the sustainability of the local area, in turn strengthening ocean literacy efforts across the local communities.

Ocean Literacy Activity 3 – Small-Scale Fisheries Pop-Up Exhibition

July 2025 onwards

The Spanish TCL team launched a pop-up exhibition to showcase the cultural and ecological importance of small-scale fisheries in Cap de Creus. Designed as a series of 12 roll-up panels, the exhibition explores diverse themes such as the anthropology of fishing, traditional and modern fishing methods, and the social and ecological value of artisanal fisheries. Each panel combines photographs, quotes, and lessons learned, giving voice to local fishers and bringing their heritage to life. The target audiences are both small-scale fishers themselves and the wider public interested in learning about and preserving this unique coastal heritage. The exhibition provides visibility to knowledge and stories that, until now, have not been widely shared or displayed.

The exhibition is an ongoing activity and is currently on display at the headquarters of the Cap de Creus Natural Park, open to the general public. One of its strengths is portability and there are future plans for the exhibition to be showcased at different venues, events and institutions. It will be made available to stakeholders, associations, and local communities upon request for different events. Discussions are also ongoing with the Natural Park to ultimately make the exhibition a permanent feature for visitors in the near future. This Ocean Literacy activity leaves a tangible and lasting EmpowerUs legacy for the Cap de Creus community, ensuring that artisanal fishing practices and knowledge continue to be recognised and valued.

4.8 Photovoice Results

More than 40 images and narratives were collected through the EmpowerUs photovoice activity. Most of the data collectors self-identified as women, with ages ranging between 22 to 61 years old. The outcome of the EmpowerUs photovoice data collection and its dissemination is shortly summarised below.

Figure 4. “It’s Thursday and the ferry moors at Selvær with supplies for the store and inhabitants. For me, the ferry is to be or not to be for the islanders. Life or death for the small island community. Here, goods, people, and animals are transported to and from the island. An absolute necessity for being able to live out here 365 days a year.” Credit: Photovoice participant.

The photovoice data were analysed based on the presented prompt that asked participants to reflect on enabling and preventing mechanisms connected to the overarching vision to “re-direct the Blue Economy to support thriving coastal communities”. The ‘connection to the sea’ was mentioned to be enhanced by the beauty and peace of living by the coast. Limitations to reaching the seaside, such as high costs, coastal development, and transportation, were revealed as hindrances to the connection. Local activities, such as festivals, and local transportation (Figure 4), were cited to contribute to the ‘promotion of communities’ well-being and/or vitality’. In contrast, a mindset of contentment was mentioned as a limitation. Finally, to ‘benefit from the sea and/or its resources’ was explained to be enabled through, for example, the economic value of seafood, while being prevented by the poor health of the ocean. There was an overall even distribution of photos that were submitted to identify enabling and preventing mechanisms between the TCLs.

4.9 Blue Justice Stories

A total of 19 Blue Justice stories were collected throughout the duration of the project, covering a range of different communities, themes, issues and injustices. All 19 stories can be found on the [EmpowerUs StoryMap](#), available on the EmpowerUs website and the EmpowerCoast Digital Platform.

Bulgaria Blue Justice Stories

1. The Chengene Skele Fishing Village Transformation

[Link to story here](#)

This story explains the history of Chengene Skele, a fishing village that came about after the displacement of fishermen from the Port of Burgas. One of the most prominent voices for the Chengene Skele fishing village, Georgi “Chicagoto” Dinev is a fisherman who has lived and fished all over the world before returning to Bulgaria. He tells the story of his experience being displaced to Chengene Skele and how the community of fishermen created new opportunities for themselves there.

2. LessPlastic Bulgaria – Embracing a Less Plastic Tomorrow

[Link to story here](#)

This story is about ongoing efforts to tackle the environmental issue of single-use plastic pollution along the Bulgarian coastline by a local NGO called LessPlastic Bulgaria. LessPlastic Bulgaria is a foundation based in the coastal municipality of Sozopol dedicated to raising awareness about single-use plastics, sharing scientific insights about their impact, recyclability, and environmental consequences. The organisation actively monitors plastic pollution along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, organises coastal cleanups, conducts independent research, and tracks waste trends. Thanks to the support of countless volunteers, over 6,800 kg of waste has been collected through its initiatives. A standout effort among its activities is the signature annual campaign, "Clean Christmas."

Nikola Bobchev (Founder), Stiliana Stoyanova (Content and Social Media Engagement Creative) and Rosen Bobchev (Tech Support) have been instrumental figures in driving the initiative forward. With its annual clean-up initiatives and engagement actions, the LessPlastic Community has over 1,400 like-minded people taking parts in their campaigns.

3. Just conservation? Greenpeace propose MPA at Black Sea coast

[Link to story here](#)

This story discusses the complexity of blue (in)justice and the potential impacts of not only blue growth but also marine conservation efforts to raise the spectre of injustice even when acting in good faith. The story's protagonists are, on the one hand, activists from Greenpeace Bulgaria engaged with the cause of improving biodiversity conservation in the Black Sea and, on the other hand, the local communities of Sozopol, Primorsko, and Tsarevo living in the municipalities adjacent to the proposed marine protected areas.

Cyprus Blue Justice Stories

1. Uneven coastal development in the Eastern Limassol Region

[Link to story here](#)

The Eastern Limassol Region, stretching along the coast, is home to several communities who live amidst a mosaic of public, community, and agricultural land. Rich in biodiversity and cultural heritage, the area also bears the weight of decades of industrialisation. This story highlights how top-down decisions have undervalued the region and shaped its trajectory, often at the expense of both the environment and local communities.

2. More than human: Mediterranean Monk Seals & Blue Justice

[Link to story here](#)

This story highlights the injustices faced by Mediterranean monk seal populations in Eastern Limassol. The Mediterranean Monk Seal (*Monachus monachus*) is Europe's most endangered marine mammal and is listed as "vulnerable" on the IUCN Red List. Once abundant across the Mediterranean and Atlantic coasts, the species has disappeared from most of its historical range. In Cyprus, only an estimated 17–20 individuals remain, highlighting both the fragility of the population and the urgency of conservation efforts.

3. Planning In Absentia: Blue Justice, Displacement & Conflict

[Link to story here](#)

This story aims to highlight the (blue) injustices faced by displaced members of the community of Pentakomo who owned coastal land, but whose experiences, cultures, and views have not been taken into consideration during decisions regarding the future of the community's coastal and marine area. This story is a reflection on the lack of involvement of members of the Turkish Cypriot Community who were living in Pentakomo, some of whom owned coastal land, prior to the division of the island in 1974.

Finland Blue Justice Stories

1. Sustainability Certification Impacts on Small-scale Fishers

[Link to story here](#)

A small group of 5–10 small-scale coastal fishers on the Åland Islands continue to practise traditional Baltic herring fishing with deep nets (*skötar*). For generations, this low-impact fishery has sustained livelihoods, preserved cultural heritage, and provided local food security. However, these fishermen face several blue injustices, with market dynamics and certification requirements now threatening its survival.

2. The Ålandic Spring Hunting – Tradition Vs Conservation

[Link to story here](#)

For generations, the people of Åland, living amidst the archipelago, have relied on the local waters and engaged with the sea. Hunting specific seabirds during the spring migration has been an integral part of this relationship, woven into the cultural fabric and seasonal rhythms of the islands.

This story addresses the conflicts between these cultural traditions in Åland and environmental regulations that were introduced to protect various seabird species.

3. Invisible threats and lost livelihoods on the Åland Islands

[Link to story here](#)

Fishing has been central to life in the Åland Islands for centuries. Once a cornerstone of food security and local culture, fishing provided both nourishment and identity for coastal communities. Today, however, health-related blue injustices exist, with small-scale fishers facing severe challenges, particularly from pollution-driven health concerns surrounding Baltic herring, salmon, and other oily fish.

Ireland Blue Justice Stories

1. Barriers to Wind Energy: The Aran Island Community Story

[Link to story here](#)

The Aran Islands, off the west coast of Ireland, are home to a close-knit community determined to shape its own sustainable future. Through Comharchumann Fuinnimh Oileáin Árann Teoranta (CFOAT), the Aran Islands Energy Cooperative, residents have united around the goal of producing their own renewable energy. Despite near-unanimous local support, restrictive planning laws, inadequate infrastructure, and exclusion from decision-making have prevented the community from developing local wind energy, leaving the islands dependent on costly and unreliable mainland electricity.

2. Island community need for a public wastewater treatment

[Link to story here](#)

The Aran Islands, a designated EU Special Area of Conservation and a world-renowned cultural and natural heritage site, attract more than 250,000 visitors each year. Yet, despite their ecological importance and the economic value they bring to Galway and Ireland, the main village of Kilronan on Inis Mór still lacks a proper public wastewater treatment facility. This failure has created an ongoing injustice for island residents who feel ignored by state authorities despite decades of calls for action.

3. Rejuvenation of native Irish oyster and scallop fisheries

[Link to story here](#)

In the bays of Cill Chiaráin and Beirtreach Buí in Conamara, generations of fishers built their livelihoods around shellfish. For decades, the community depended on a balance of fishing, farming, seaweed cutting, and seasonal incomes to survive. But the collapse of the native oyster and scallop fishery, once a reliable and vital source of income, has threatened both livelihoods and traditions. The story of Comharchumann Sliogéisc Chonamara, a co-operative now under renewed leadership, reflects the resilience of fishers who are working to restore their fisheries while highlighting the structural injustices faced by small marine enterprises.

4. The Ban on fishing pollock on the Connemara Coast

[Link to story here](#)

On the Connemara coast, pollock fishing has long been part of the livelihood of inshore fishers, practiced through sustainable, selective line fishing handed down over generations. For fishers like Séamus Breathnach, with over 40 years of experience, and his son, the pollock fishery represented both pride in tradition and a vital source of income. However, the EU's recent ban on pollock fishing in Irish waters has shaken this tradition, leaving communities frustrated, disillusioned, and uncertain about the future.

Norway Blue Justice Stories

1. World Heritage Sites: Justice for heritage but not for all

[Link to story here](#)

This Blue Justice story is one regarding the inequitable distribution of economic benefits, and the social and cultural inequalities of ocean development and conservation. It deals with the World Heritage Site on the Vega Islands in Norway that was developed for the purpose of conserving cultural heritage of specific traditions, in this case eider duck husbandry, but this may be at the detriment to other cultural practices or modern growth needs. Many stakeholders, including local tradition keepers, artists, fish farmers, politicians, fishers, farmers, academics, and wider community members on the islands, have experienced both the positive and negative impacts as a result of the World Heritage Site status.

2. Connecting the Coastline: Transport and Justice in Helgeland

[Link to story here](#)

This Blue Justice story highlights the experiences of local island communities and local politicians from island municipalities with the fragile transportation system along the coast of Helgeland. This piece illustrates how transportation access is fundamental to sustaining life, identity, and opportunity along Norway's remote coastlines, ensuring issues with social inequity and rural marginalisation are avoided.

3. Welcoming the World, Protecting the Island: Tourism in Træna

[Link to story here](#)

This Blue Justice Story explores the case of tourism in Træna, a small island municipality on the Helgeland coast in Northern Norway. With only around 460 residents, Træna is known internationally for its music festival, Trænafestivalen. In recent years, the municipality has worked actively to develop a tourism strategy that protects the island, while also welcoming the world. This story takes a closer look at the community's reflections around cruise ships, camper vans, and the annual festival, and how they've found ways to balance local needs with visitor interests.

Spain Blue Justice Stories

1. From Traditional Small-scale Fishing to Modern Barriers

[Link to story here](#)

This blue justice story centres around 'M', a small-scale fisher based in Llançà, Catalonia, Spain who began fishing at the age of 10 with his uncles and had mastered the trade by 14. Today, he tends a vegetable garden in his village, reflecting how his livelihood has shifted over time due to profound changes in the fishing sector.

2. Strength in Unity: Fishers of Cap de Creus

[Link to story here](#)

Along the rugged coastline of Cap de Creus in Catalonia, fishing has been more than a livelihood to the local community members. It has been heritage, identity, and a way of caring for the Mediterranean Sea. For generations, artisanal fishers practised low-impact, small-scale fishing, guided by the confraries (fishing guilds) that structured community life. Yet over the past two decades, new pressures, including conservation restrictions, globalised seafood markets, and tourism, have placed their way of life under threat. In response, the fishers united across three guilds and one community to form OPP-96, the Cap de Creus Fish Producers' Organisation, a pioneering example of solidarity, stewardship, and Blue Justice in action.

3. Women's Voices for a Sustainable Sea in Cap de Creus

[Link to story here](#)

This story takes place in Port de la Selva, on the Catalan coast, where two women are charting a course for a fairer and more sustainable relationship with the sea. Elena Manera, a boat captain, and Pat Bros, a fisher and environmental educator, are among the few professional women in Catalonia's small-scale fisheries. Their work connects fishing, science, and cultural education, embodying leadership that integrates Blue Justice, sustainability, and community empowerment.

4.10 Resources delivered to improve ocean literacy

EmpowerUs initially committed to deliver 12 ocean literacy resources across the TCLs. In total, 22 resources were delivered, including resources specific to various TCLs as well as other resources for wider audiences (Table 3).

Table 3. Overview of Ocean Literacy Resources produced.

TCL	Target Audience	Ocean Literacy Resources
Bulgaria	Decision makers, funders, researchers, environmental authorities, organisations and nonprofits.	<p><i>Policy brief: Ocean & Society in Bulgaria National Ocean Literacy Needs for an Empowered and Resilient Future</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This policy brief summarises the results of the Ocean & Society survey conducted in Bulgaria and presents: Society's understanding of challenges facing the coast in Bulgaria; Empowerment needs to tackle the challenges Bulgarian communities face for a more resilient future; and ocean literacy-focused recommendations based on the survey findings in Bulgaria. <p><i>Resources at the Renovated Avocet Trail at Atanasovsko Lake³</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The newly renovated Avocet Trail now features many new resources, including updated educational signs along the trail and observation points so visitors can connect better with the lake's biodiversity.
Cyprus	Decision makers, funders, researchers, environmental authorities, organisations and nonprofits.	<p><i>Policy brief: Ocean & Society in Cyprus National Ocean Literacy Needs for an Empowered and Resilient Future</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This policy brief summarises the results of the Ocean & Society survey conducted in Cyprus and presents: Society's understanding of challenges facing the coast in Cyprus; Empowerment needs to tackle the challenges Cypriot communities face for a more resilient future; and ocean literacy-focused recommendations based on the survey findings in Cyprus. <p><i>Cape Dolos Strategic Community Development Plan⁴</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is the main output of the Cyprus pilot initiative that was developed to map ecological, social and cultural values of the coastal region to inform the development of future initiatives that connect local people and the sea.
Finland	Decision makers, funders, researchers, environmental authorities, organisations and nonprofits. Water owners	<p><i>Policy brief: Ocean & Society in Finland National Ocean Literacy Needs for an Empowered and Resilient Future</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This policy brief summarises the results of the Ocean & Society survey conducted in Finland and presents: Society's understanding of challenges facing the coast in Finland; Empowerment needs to tackle the challenges Finnish communities face for a more resilient future; and ocean literacy-focused recommendations based on the survey findings in Finland. <p><i>Cherish our Fishing Waters (Vårda Våra Fiskevatten) Campaign Leaflet</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This leaflet was sent to 15,750 households across the Åland Islands and highlighted to community members how to check if you own

³ [D2.3 EmpowerUs Impact Brief, Bulgaria: The power of community anchors.](#)

⁴ [D2.3 EmpowerUs Impact Brief, Cyprus: Community-driven coastal transformations.](#)

		<p>water on Åland and your rights and obligations as a water owner. The TCL team also included useful information on the leaflet about where you can find funding for projects that benefit the ocean and information about what we can do to stop the most destructive actions in shallow water areas which are some of the most productive and biodiverse but also where almost everything is within the realm of private ownership since hundreds of years.</p> <p>Practical Fisheries Management Resource website⁵</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A website for water owners, fishers and those who want to get involved in water stewardship on the Åland Islands to provide them with the guidance, resources and tools to develop initiatives to protect and restore Åland’s waters. <p><i>Herring Fishing Exhibition</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A permanent interactive exhibition at the Hunting and Fishing Museum in Eckerö, Åland to promote Traditional herring fishing with gill nets as one of the most important expressions of Åland’s coastal culture and heritage.
Ireland	Decision makers, funders, researchers, environmental authorities, organisations and nonprofits.	<p><i>Policy brief: Ocean & Society in Ireland National Ocean Literacy Needs for an Empowered and Resilient Future</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This policy brief summarises the results of the Ocean & Society survey conducted in Ireland and presents: Society’s understanding of challenges facing the coast in Ireland; Empowerment needs to tackle the challenges Irish communities face for a more resilient future; and ocean literacy-focused recommendations based on the survey findings in Ireland. <p>Marine Identities Workshop Methodology Booklet</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is a guidance document for ocean literacy practitioners who are interested in running their own Marine Identities Workshops, based on the workshop co-organised by Queen’s University Belfast, Údarás na Gaeltachta and the Irish Ocean Literacy Network (IOLN) at the IOLN Regional Meeting held in Lettermullan, Galway, Ireland in May 2025. <p>Webinar on Reflections on Marine Identities – Online Recording</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The joint webinar on Reflections of Marine Identities in collaboration with the Irish Ocean Literacy Network was recorded and shared on YouTube to allow ocean literacy practitioners from Ireland and further afield to gain insights into how the workshop could be replicated in other locations and contexts.
Norway	Decision makers, funders, researchers, environmental authorities, organisations and nonprofits.	<p><i>Policy brief: Ocean & Society in Norway National Ocean Literacy Needs for an Empowered and Resilient Future</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This policy brief summarises the results of the Ocean & Society survey conducted in Norway and presents: Society’s understanding of challenges facing the coast in Norway; Empowerment needs to tackle the challenges Norwegian communities face for a more resilient future; and ocean literacy-focused recommendations based on the survey findings in Norway. <p><i>Hekta på Træna (Hooked on Træna) Treasure Hunt activity materials</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging materials were produced for the Hekta på Træna Treasure Hunt at the Træna Festival 2024, including treasure hunt maps and stamp sheets for each participant. The activity also saw the launch of the official Hekta på Træna branding and logo that was subsequently used as the official branding for the entire Hekta på Træna pilot initiative. <p><i>Our Blue Cultural Heritage: 26 cultural trail posts and stories</i></p>

⁵ [D2.3 EmpowerUs Impact Brief: Finland. Åland and the coast as a common pool resource.](#)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In collaboration with the national orienteering app 'Stolpejakten', 26 local heritage stories were collected and are showcased at 26 different posts around the islands of Træna.
Spain	Decision makers, funders, researchers, environmental authorities, organisations and nonprofits.	<p><i>Policy brief: Ocean & Society in Spain National Ocean Literacy Needs for an Empowered and Resilient Future</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This policy brief summarises the results of the Ocean & Society survey conducted in Spain and presents: Society's understanding of challenges facing the coast in Spain; Empowerment needs to tackle the challenges Spanish communities face for a more resilient future; and ocean literacy-focused recommendations based on the survey findings in Spain. <p>NaturCap Web App⁶</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A community co-created digital platform promoting responsible tourism that includes interactive quizzes, emotional mapping, and storytelling to foster environmental awareness and cultural connection. <p><i>Cap de Creus Video Capsules</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A series of audiovisual clips produced to highlight the local values of Cap de Creus, including the community connections with the ocean. The series features videos on the following topics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food Sovereignty: Video link. Healthy Seas: Video link. Heritage: Video link. Silences & Noises: Video link. Women & The Sea: Video link. Compilation Video: Video link. <p><i>Small-scale Fisheries Pop-up Exhibition Roll-up Panels</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A portable exhibition of 12 roll-up panels that showcase the stories of small-scale fishers in Cap de Creus.
Other	European and international level policymakers (e.g. European Commission, Ocean Decade), funders, researchers, projects (e.g. EU4Ocean and BlueLights), environmental authorities, organisations and nonprofits.	<p><i>Policy brief: Ocean & Society Survey European Ocean Literacy Needs for an Empowered and Resilient Future</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This policy brief summarises the overarching results of the Ocean & Society survey conducted across the six EmpowerUs countries and presents: Society's understanding of challenges facing European coasts; Empowerment needs to tackle the challenges European communities face for a more resilient future; and ocean literacy-focused recommendations based on the survey findings across the six EmpowerUs countries. <p>Women Making Waves Ocean Literacy Activity Book</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This activity book serves as an educational and inspirational ocean literacy resource for kids, marine educators and ocean literacy practitioners that showcases real-life stories of women who have contributed to marine science, conservation, coastal livelihoods, the arts and coastal community activism. The idea first started as a social media campaign, celebrating women from the six EmpowerUs TCL countries who inspire or are inspired by the ocean, and their significant contributions to the marine environment. The stories collected for the campaign were adapted and included in the activity book, along with various exercises inspired by the women's stories. The Women Making Waves Activity Book was initially published in English in June 2025 and has since been translated to Norwegian, Greek, Bulgarian and Irish. <p><i>Photovoices</i></p>

⁶ D2.3. EmpowerUs Impact Brief. Spain: Digital reach, communities and a responsible coast.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Photovoices act as an ocean literacy resource to showcase the connections between coastal community members and the ocean. The Photovoices collected and posters produced can be used as inspiring resources to encourage other target groups and communities to think about their connections to the ocean, including how the ocean impacts them and how they impact the ocean too. <p><i>Blue Justice stories</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The blue justice stories are resources that highlight the lived local experiences of navigating the impacts of the blue economy and blue growth on coastal communities, touching upon several ocean literacy dimensions, in particular emoceans, trust and transparency, and access.
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4.11 Summary of the dimensions of Ocean Literacy nurtured by EmpowerUs

Between October 2022 and September 2025, EmpowerUs has delivered 27 activities strategically through targeted ocean literacy activities in the 6 host country TCLs, 3 at international events, and 22 resources. Although each activity aimed to target at least one Essential Principle of Ocean Science, most focused instead on nurturing ocean connections through dimensions beyond knowledge. Of the 30 activities targeted to improve ocean literacy: all 30 nurtured peoples **awareness** of ocean issues, 27 aspired to improve **communication** about ocean topics, 26 focused at least in part on improving **attitudes**, 25 nurtured the **knowledge** dimension; 24 touched peoples **emoceans**; 22 enabled **access & experience**; 18 aspired to inspire improved **behaviours** for the ocean; 13 hoped to improve **trust & transparency** between actors; 11 focused on encouraging **activism**, and 8 considered providing strategies and tools to improve **adaptive capacity**.

Although all dimensions may have been touched by activities, we wanted to assess the strength of the focus on dimensions across the project (quality rather than quantity), rather than engage in a deep evaluation. Each activity was scored 0-3 for each dimension; where 0 = no contribution; 1 = not the focus of the activity, but the dimension may be nurtured as a side impact; 2 = some deliberate focus; 3 = the main focus(es) of the activity. The average scores are presented in Figure 5, showing that raising awareness was the strongest focus across the project, followed by knowledge.

Awareness and knowledge are often confused, and from descriptions given by organisers, knowledge may have been over scored. Conversely, activities did not have a heavy focus on ‘adaptive capacity’, or ‘trust and transparency’, and these could be areas for further targeted work on projects like EmpowerUs. Surveys found that universities and researchers are trusted actors, whereas communities, governments and businesses are less so. One of the key recommendations is to promote the ocean literacy potential within transdisciplinary projects as a way of working, as co-creation between trusted and less trusted actors should improve ocean literacy through these dimensions.

The text below demonstrates specific examples of how EmpowerUs has engaged novelly across the TCL, with content provided from the evaluation forms from event organisers.

Figure 5: Contributions of the targeted activities across EmpowerUs to the different dimensions of ocean literacy (including 27 activities across 6 TCL, plus 3 international events). Bubbles represent the average contribution of activities to this dimension, when scored from 0-3. Larger bubbles represent the stronger focus of activities (on average across project) to this dimension (adapted from McKinley et al., 2023)

Knowledge: ‘Knowledge has multiple aspects. In the first instance, knowledge is what a person knows about an ocean related topic and the links between topics. Knowledge also refers to the knowledge a person has about ocean decision-making, opportunities to participate and engage in ocean decisions and behaviours and where/ how to get information about ocean issues’ (McKinley et al., 2023)

Knowledge, as McKinley et al. define, is a deeper understanding of topics than awareness, including knowledge of how to participate in decision making. However, knowledge and awareness are closely related and have probably been confused between activity organisers.

Most activities focused primarily on Principle 5: The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems (22/30 activities) and Principle 6: The ocean and humans are inextricably interconnected (22/30 activities). The least engaged knowledge Principle was 7: The ocean is largely unexplored (n=2) and Principle 3: The ocean is a major influence on weather and climate (n=4). There was more potential for TCL to work with principle 3 in the context of sustainable transitions, but the activities were limited to the interests of the host organization and to ideally support the overarching pilot and project aims.

That said, each activity worked differently, focusing on different aspects of knowledge. At least two activities focused on capturing and re-telling local knowledge (such as a citizen science event in Bulgaria, and a marine identity workshop in Ireland), as did the photovoice and blue justice activities.

Awareness: is ‘the basic knowledge and understanding that a situation, problem or concept exists. Awareness should also include knowledge and understanding of the solutions and behaviours that may exist to address these problems in order to foster ownership and empower society to take action.’ (McKinley et al., 2023)

All activities focused on raising awareness, from awareness of species (Cyprus), spawning grounds (Finland), access rights (Bulgaria) to wider issues about marine management and our One Ocean (Norway). Spain produced a digital tool to continue raising awareness of our human-ocean connection, and continues networking with people and advertising events, beyond the EmpowerUs Project (as a UN Endorsed Ocean Decade Activity).

Attitudes: ‘Attitude is related to a level of agreement with or concern for a particular position. Attitude should also include consideration of perceptions, values, and views towards an ocean issue, and how these can lead to policy and societal change.’ (McKinley et al., 2023)

Attitude is a dimension that may have been over-reported in the ocean literacy summaries. Many cited that attitudes were known to be influenced by increased awareness and knowledge. However, many did give good examples of how and why they worked with attitudes. For instance, in Cyprus there has been some local discontent over designation of a local marine protected area, so a carefully developed activity wanted to tackle this attitude amongst children, in hope that they communicate this with their elders. An event took school children to several research institutes and venues, to experience the space, but also learn about species and how data is collected and monitored. As a result, they were also building trust, transparency and emotions amongst others.

Communication: ‘Communication in the context of ocean literacy must be considered from multiple perspectives. 1) Communication is the extent to which a person communicates with others, such as family and peer groups, on ocean related topics. 2) Communication should also consider how/ where people get their information about ocean issues from –What methods of communication are most effective? 3) At an organisational level, communication needs to consider how institutions and organisations are communicating to different audiences about ocean issues.’ (McKinley et al., 2023)

“Developing the ocean literacy activities with the community of Traena, focused on raising the profile of their strong cultural connection to the sea, and ‘havfolk’ (sea people) identity to outsiders, helped to shape the final pilot project. Conversations had engaged members of the community who were not previously engaged, raised the profile of the project within the wider community and inspired conversations around the sustainability (including great attendance at the final EmpowerUs event) that may not have otherwise occurred. Ultimately, the branding developed during the ocean literacy activities ‘Hekta på Træna’ was adopted for the resulting ‘pilot strategy’: a strategy that brings together all of the work undertaken by EmpowerUs, with useful tools and strategies to help them continue the work into the future.”

Meanwhile, in Bulgaria, university art students undertook ocean education, and designed a new conservation area logo *“The newly created logo (created by students as part of this activity) will be the vision and will communicate the Burgas protected area – a remarkable place of international importance, the richest bird habitat (334 species) and the only place where sea salt is produced in Bulgaria, a deposit of therapeutic mud and salt marshes.”*

Ireland focused its activities around the concept of Marine Identity, where participants communicated their marine identities to each other. Their workshop invited the public and members of the maritime

sectors to come together to explore what the marine space means to them, through presentations and guided discussions centred around objects and photographs that people brought with them. The follow-up webinar acted as a conversation starter, facilitating further communication about people's connections to the sea.

“The conversations sparked during this webinar clearly showed that marine identity resonates deeply with people across Ireland and beyond. By bringing together diverse voices and experiences, marine identity can contribute toward more inclusive and place-based approaches to ocean literacy and stewardship.” – Alex Miller (QUB).

Activism: *‘Activism is the degree to which a person engages in a wide range of activities, which can constitute activism, such as campaigning (for example through social media, attending public rallies or writing to elected officials) to bring about changes in policy, attitudes, behaviour, etc. Understanding this dimension must also take account of who gets to participate in activism and what the barriers might be.’* (McKinley et al., 2023)

The Burgas TCL team organised a corporate activism event with a local bank, getting staff to volunteer, preserve the ecosystem, and install signage about the local sand dunes. In Finland, the water stewardship campaign was successful in touching upon the activism dimension. “The outcomes of the activity were that we gathered parts of the water owning community in a new forum, giving water owners a community to tackle the problems of the coast together for the first time.”

Behaviour: *‘Behaviour relates to decisions, choices, actions, and habits with respect to ocean related issues at a range of scales, including from individual, sector and policy actors and institutions with a view to bringing about whole system change.’* (McKinley et al., 2023)

Novel approaches were used to engage different actors to engage with this dimension of ocean literacy. In particular, through one event in Bulgaria, the project engaged local garage employees to become stewards for the Avocet trail. Through their involvement, it is hoped that they will become more proactive citizens in environmental stewardship.

Emoceans: *‘Emotional connections is about how a person feels and emotionally responds when they think about, are near/within, or consider issues relating to the ocean, coasts and seas. Emotions can be positive, negative or neutral and are all valid responses and will all contribute to behaviour change.’* (McKinley et al., 2023)

Many activities touched upon emoceans, such as biodiversity carnivals in Bulgaria, connecting children and families to the ocean in an emotive and memorable way through storytelling, music and recycled costumes. In Traena, participants explored emoceans through a collaborative fishing heritage and food event at the Winterfestival: “It is important to connect different academic environments and local communities/countries together in order to learn about and from each other – to find common challenges and opportunities.” The Cyprus event, “Here Only Monachus” aimed to connect children with marine life, particularly monk seals, by fostering a creative and emotional connection to the ocean.

Access & Experience: *‘Access and experience relate to a person's real or artificial (through Virtual Reality, for example) experiences and engagement with the ocean, and the various ways in which they can access these experiences. Barriers to ocean access and experiences should also be considered within this dimension.’* (McKinley et al., 2023)

Cycling events in Burgas “familiarised people with new parts of their environment, making them better aware they have access” The events also “familiarised many with the available bike paths and also raised awareness for the need for better access in places” to connect people to the sea. In Cyprus, at the “Here Only Monachus” workshops, these events “provided a unique sensory experience by using seal sounds and creative activities to bring the ocean closer to the participants.”

Adaptive Capacity: *‘Adaptive capacity relates to a person’s capacity to adapt and respond to changing conditions relating to their ocean (e.g., relating to climate change, change in ocean economies, or changing ecosystem structure or function).’* (McKinley et al., 2023)

The event in Burgas, ‘Climate evolution: Are we ready for the new climate?’, dealt with adaptive capacity through “An educational, musical and inspiring event about climate change and our preparation for it”. This was an interactive event, where students and other participants could take an active role in discussing the communities adaptive capacity needs.

Trust & Transparency: *‘Trust and transparency relate to the level of trust a person places in sources of ocean information and knowledge, and their perception of how transparent information and associated platforms and processes are.’* (McKinley et al., 2023)

Building trust can start at a young age. In Cyprus there has been distrust in the designation process of an MPA. Activities focused on reconnecting primary school children with the oceans and life in the ocean, but also introducing where information comes from and how it is evidenced. In Bulgaria, Local businesses took part in corporate activism and learned where scientific data came from, how sites were established and in doing so, built trust in how conservation works, and why. In Finland, Workshops demonstrated the importance of ‘trust building’ between the experts that suggest actions and the local community that will perform them, leading to positive environmental outcomes. Ideally, the trust building should be continued through participatory monitoring with the community.

4. Ocean literacy as a mechanism for empowerment during transformative change.

EmpowerUs set out to deliver meaningful ocean literacy that was both aligned with project goals but also worked to improve societal ocean literacy. First and foremost the project focuses on socio-economic empowerment of coastal communities, which we used in two ways in this work package: first through national surveys that aimed to link three dimensions of empowerment to ocean literacy; and second used the three pillars of empowerment introduced in D3.2 / 4.2 (based on Avelino 2017), together with the current dimensions of ocean literacy, to develop meaningful ocean education resources and activities that are empowering, to help coastal communities face their transitions.

National surveys: how does ocean literacy influence empowerment to tackle community and sustainability challenges?

National surveys of ocean, society and empowerment, we revealed that well-being, and to a lesser extent socio-demographics, were the dominant drivers of how much knowledge people feel they have to overcome general challenges in their community, and how much access to resources and tools people feel that they have to help them and their communities thrive (in keeping with Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs and theories of motivation that people’s needs must be met before they can connect, learn, and thrive, Maslow, 1943). However, environmental connection seemed an important driver of willingness to participate in actions to make their community more sustainable ocean literate in the dimensions of awareness, oceans, connected through access in certain ways, and trust in different actors. **Increasing ocean awareness** (how much do people agree that the ocean influences them, and their actions influence the ocean) is a strong predictor of how empowered people are to act for the ocean and their challenges, along all three pillars of empowerment.

Emoceans (even strong negative ones, such as anxiety and fear) and interest are important in empowering people, especially linked to people’s willingness to change their lifestyles for the ocean, but also in participating in actions to make their community more sustainable and feeling as though they have the knowledge they need to tackle the challenges they face. Emoceans were not important influences on peoples’ feelings of how much they have to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for them as a person—or for their community—to thrive. **Increasing trust** the government to act to address ocean threats, they may well take less personal responsibility. This negative relationship between trust in government, and willingness to take action was seen in both ocean and more general community contexts. **Higher trust in local communities and small businesses was** linked to significantly more access to the resources people need to help them and their community thrive.

Access to resources seemed to appear the least empowered dimension in both the national surveys, and local TCL surveys (closely linked to D3.2, Spiering et al., 2025a). Whilst these national results confirm broad willingness to participate in community actions, local findings using deeper qualitative interviews, reveal the persistent barriers of fairness, resources, and recognition that must be addressed to turn this willingness into real transition. Bridging these perspectives will be essential for linking national strategies with the lived realities of coastal communities, for instance in delivering ocean literacy strategies that support empowering resource development that enables real changes to people’s lives and ocean health (Spiering et al., 2025a).

EmpowerUs acknowledges that global survey tools like this only provide rapid assessments of a nation’s opinion, and online survey panels can be a barrier to Leaving No One Behind, as national surveys do not take into account minority views, so more research is needed to account for place specific variations. But Broad findings from these surveys give us information to help develop future ocean literacy materials, with different people, noting that communicators must ensure strong messaging that we can, and should, make positive changes in our lives for the benefit of the ocean, even when we believe our governments are strengthening their actions. The surveys also acted as ocean literacy resources for policy makers, as policy briefs in a language they can connect with. The resulting policy briefs “Ocean literacy needs for an empowered and resilient future” recommend that to Leave No One Behind, funders must support ocean literacy and place-based research to develop strategic communication plans (EmpowerUs 2025). This recommendation is echoed in D5.3, Policy Brief “An Equitable Ocean Pact? Leaving No One Behind in Just Coastal Community Transitions”.

Co-development of meaningful ocean education resources and activities that are empowering, to help coastal communities face their transitions

Our place based approach to the co-creation of ocean literacy activities and materials used a dialogue rooted in the 3 pillars of empowerment (strategies, access, and willingness) to successfully engage a wide range of citizens in 30 activities (Table 2, Section 4.1), deliver a plethora of resources (Table 4.3, Section 4.10) and nurture ocean literate participants in dimensions other than knowledge (Figure 5, Section 4.11). In some cases, our approach to this, centred around Avelino’s definition of empowerment, worked to develop ocean dialogues and co-develop activities and resources that were meaningful, targeted to specific audiences for maximum effect. In other cases, how the ocean literacy agenda could align with the local EmpowerUs pilot was less clear, and sometimes hindered by issues around justice, power, equity and agency, and other times considered an inappropriate tool ([D2.3 Cyprus Impact Brief on community-driven coastal transformations](#); D5.2, Morris-Webb et al.,

2025b). Gustavsson (2025) presents a framework on how to negotiate a Leaving No One Behind manifesto in projects like this. Our experience is in keeping with EmpowerUs findings across the project, that show that such strategies, and Just Transition Mechanisms, can only succeed if principles of blue justice are addressed: recognitional (acknowledging diverse groups and knowledge systems), distributional (ensuring local communities benefit fairly), and procedural (ensuring meaningful participation in decision-making) (EmpowerUs Policy Brief: Coastal Transition Mechanisms, Ounanian 2025).

However, in some cases, where topics were not too sensitive, carefully planned, deep ocean dialogues such as the photovoice reflections, marine identity workshops, collation of anonymous (or public) blue justice stories and, perhaps most strongly, trails centred around the local culture of the sea served to act as conversation starters, or door openers, centred on topics that people were passionate that researchers understand, before developing the research or producing knowledge outputs that have not taken into account the local knowledge.

The most important findings from the project were that ocean literacy can be used as a tool, or mechanism for empowerment. Although not initially considered important, the TCL increasingly saw the value of the conversations being had, especially with the community and organisations involved with co-creating activities. The three most important mechanisms identified were:

- **Ocean literacy through strengthening and emphasising cultural connection and marine identities:**

“The need to describe these traditional and sustainable fishing activities has become clear throughout Empower Us on Åland, to make the intangible tangible in some way or form.” Viktor Eriksson, talking about the late addition of the herring exhibition to the Finnish pilot project. An idea shared with Træna, and they too have worked with a museum to curate a local exhibition in their final pilot.

- **Ocean literacy as conversation starters, to bring people into the sustainability dialogues, and build trust within the team.**

In Spain conversations started at a food sovereignty event that led to a new food sovereignty forum *“A significant milestone was establishing this first forum, enabling the local community to lead future follow-ups. It leverages existing resources like signage and spaces, with strong support from local government and the Cap de Creus Natural Park administration. The project’s potential for continuation by the TCL members ensures sustainability and engagement”* Silvia Gomez

- **Co-creation is key!**

It wasn’t always just the resource or activity that was empowering – most of the direct empowerment felt was in the co-creation of these resources with the community, and through effective co-creation, the legacy and pathway to increase wider ocean literacy is improved. Blue Justice, women making waves, and even co-developing trails open discussions with members of the community that inspires further involvement and fosters deeper connection with the research team (both in Træna, Burgas and Åland). This is in keeping with recent work that finds co-creation is empowering as the act of listening and valuing knowledge and feelings / meanings

of communities nurtures reciprocity, and ocean literacy, or equitable ocean dialogues, can create a framework for that (LaMontagne & Graham, 2025.) These careful dialogues, and co-creation, can build trust that is essential in any decision making, or transdisciplinary project.

Areas for further work

More place based research will help future transdisciplinary projects like EmpowerUs. Activities did not have a heavy focus on ‘adaptive capacity’, or ‘trust and transparency’, and these could be areas for further targeted work on projects like EmpowerUs that focus on community centered resilience solutions. With this in mind, there was more potential for TCL to work with principle 3 in the context of sustainable transitions, but the activities were limited to the interests of the host organization and to ideally support the overarching pilot and project aims.

5. Conclusion

The EmpowerUs project has successfully implemented meaningful ocean literacy activities, that often aligned with the wider project goals, as well as the broader ocean literacy agenda. We did this through bringing the EmpowerUs pillars of empowerment to frame our approach to designing educational interventions across the project, ensuring our TCL partners have access, strategies and willingness to deliver meaningful ocean literacy. Key results were that the ocean dialogues that take part when co-creating these activities, especially when around identity and cultural heritage, are a key mechanism to empowerment. We know that our activities have been empowering as we touched the hearts and minds, improving ocean literacy, not just of the TCL hosts, but also for all those involved in co-creation to consider and needs of the sea and coastal communities, in their discussions and decisions, reaching from the home and classrooms, to high level panels and national ocean policy makers and funders.

The UN Decade for the Ocean has recognised that we now have more knowledge than people can digest, so the challenge facing us in the second half of the decade is bringing society (from researchers in different disciplines, business and industry, to individual people) on board with accepting and tackling the changes we need to make. Embedding strategic ocean literacy and communication is key, as an enabling factor for these conversations, taking into account trust and transparency and ocean connection. This is acknowledged by the ocean decade, and storytelling and communicating will be important in the future of the European Ocean Pact.

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7. Appendices

Appendix 1: Ocean Literacy activity reporting template

EmpowerUs Ocean Literacy Activity Follow-up Evaluation Form

Name of Ocean Literacy activity	
Date of Ocean Literacy activity?	
Where did the Ocean Literacy activity take place?	
Which Essential Ocean Literacy Principles did this activity focus on (if any)?	Choose an item. Choose an item. Choose an item. Choose an item. Choose an item.
What was the Ocean Literacy activity about? <i>Please describe your activity, the aims of your activity and what the activity did to achieve its objectives.</i>	
Who was your target audience? <i>(Thinking of different groups of people within your TCL and approximate numbers).</i>	
Who attended the activity? <i>Please provide details on the target groups that attended. Include the number of participants.</i>	
Who organised and ran the Ocean Literacy activity?	

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<p><i>Please feel free to include individuals' names as well as the organisations if you wish.</i></p>	
<p>What were the outcomes of the activity?</p> <p><i>Were any resources produced? Did you reach any TCL goals? Any significant achievements to note as a result of the activity?</i></p>	
<p>Lessons learned?</p> <p><i>Reflecting on your challenges and successes when running this activity, please tell us what your main lessons were and how you might improve on this activity if you were doing it again in future?</i></p>	
<p>Quote(s) from TCL team member(s) about the Ocean Literacy activity:</p> <p><i>Please also provide the name(s) of TCL member(s) who provided the quote(s).</i></p>	
<p>Please add any additional relevant information here that hasn't been included yet.</p>	
<p>Please detail any photos, videos, links, that you are providing here.</p> <p><i>Media can be uploaded to the relevant TCL folder in the Ocean Literacy Activities & Resources folder on SharePoint.</i></p>	

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Thinking about how you designed and implemented your activity, please relate this to the dimensions of Ocean Literacy below.

(Dimensions from McKinley et al 2022: [The evolution of ocean literacy: A new framework for the United Nations Ocean Decade and beyond - ScienceDirect](#))

Dimension	Definition	Did your activity CONSIDER this dimension in its design? For instance, did you develop it to be sensitive to a specific dimension, without intending to change the dimension. If so, please give detail of why you designed your activity around this dimension (i.e. was there existing conflict, data revealing inequalities, etc).	Did you AIM to empower this dimension? If so, did you evaluate its success in any way?	Do you think your activity was successful (intentionally or otherwise) at EMPOWERING this OL Dimension? If so, give details.

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Appendix 2: Blue Justice story collection template & consent form

EmpowerUs Blue Justice & Blue Voices Stories – Story Collection Template

Blue Justice examines how local coastal communities are impacted by the Blue Economy and Blue Growth. It looks at how the Blue Economy/Blue Growth agenda can further marginalise and disadvantage small scale fisheries and other users of the sea through initiatives including industrial fishing, coastal and marine tourism, aquaculture and energy production.

As part of Task 6.4, each of the EmpowerUs TCL teams will collect local stories (Blue Justice stories) from their communities. These stories will be portrayed on an interactive online EmpowerUs StoryMap that will be developed in the upcoming months and will be hosted on the EmpowerUs website.

TCL teams are tasked with collecting at least 3 Blue Justice stories each which will feature on the EmpowerUs StoryMap. Examples of stories can include:

- Stories where injustices have been tackled and a solution has already been achieved,
- Stories where injustices are ongoing in the local community and the EmpowerUs project may help to achieve blue justice.

Instructions for collecting stories:

1. Identify your story and storyteller(s). This could be a community member, local business owner, or anybody in your TCL.
2. Invite your selected participant to share their story with you and ensure they consent to having their story shared publicly online.
3. Fill in the story collection template in collaboration with your storyteller(s). Make sure that the template is completed fully. Collect relevant images from the storyteller(s).
4. Once the template is complete, please return it to donnchadh@erinn.eu, along with the images for the story.

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1. Story Overview	
<p>Title of story:</p> <p><i>Please provide a short title for your Blue Justice story (no longer than 10 words).</i></p>	
<p>Theme</p> <p><i>Select the theme(s) most relevant to your story</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aquaculture <input type="checkbox"/> • Biodiversity and Conservation <input type="checkbox"/> • Climate Change <input type="checkbox"/> • Cultural Heritage <input type="checkbox"/> • Displacement <input type="checkbox"/> • Energy Production <input type="checkbox"/> • Fisheries <input type="checkbox"/> • Food Security <input type="checkbox"/> • Gender <input type="checkbox"/> • Mobility/Transportation <input type="checkbox"/> • Outmigration/Resident Retention <input type="checkbox"/> • Pollution and Waste <input type="checkbox"/> • Tourism <input type="checkbox"/> • Well-being <input type="checkbox"/> • Youth <input type="checkbox"/>
<p>Place:</p> <p><i>Where is this story from? Where does it take place?</i></p>	
<p>Link to exact location:</p> <p><i>Please provide an exact location pin from Google Maps.</i></p>	
<p>Community member(s) involved in the Story:</p> <p><i>Please provide the name(s) of the person(s) involved in the story.</i></p> <p><i>People have the option to provide pseudonyms or aliases if they wish to remain anonymous. Please indicate if the name(s) of the person(s) provided are not their real names.</i></p>	
<p>Additional information about community member(s):</p>	

<p><i>Please provide a short introductory biography about the main person(s) in your story that the injustice(s) centre around. Your story could focus on a specific individual (e.g. a fisher, a local businessperson, a local citizen, an animal, etc.) or a particular community or group of stakeholders (e.g. a local neighbourhood, a community group, local fishing group, an NGO, a natural ecosystem, etc.).</i></p>	
<p>2. Blue Justice Story</p>	
<p><i>Please write your Blue Justice story here. Below are some guiding questions to help you write your story.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Background</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What injustice(s) is being faced by the person(s) in the story?</i> • <i>When did the injustice begin? What was the cause of the injustice(s)? How did the injustice(s) begin? Who or what is responsible for the injustice(s)?</i> • <i>What was life like for the local community member(s) before the injustice(s)?</i> 2. <i>Impacts</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What have the impacts been on the local stakeholder(s) involved in the story as a result of the injustice(s)? Please provide specific examples/anecdotes if possible.</i> • <i>Has the injustice(s) evolved overtime? If so, how?</i> 3. <i>Solutions and Next Steps</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Has the injustice(s) been tackled? Has a solution to the injustice(s) been achieved? If so, how did the solution come about? What involvement did the local community member(s) have in creating/implementing the solution, if any?</i> • <i>If the injustice(s) is still ongoing, what potential solutions do the local community member(s) in the story think would help to tackle the injustice(s)? Could the EmpowerUs project help to achieve justice?</i> 	

The following questions and themes have been taken from the paper, 'Blue growth and blue justice: Ten risks and solutions for the ocean economy' (Bennett et al., 2021) available on SharePoint here: [Bennett et al 2021 Blue Growth and Blue Justice Marine Policy.pdf](#). These questions will help to elaborate and provide further details to create their stories.

Which of the following injustices feature in your Blue Justice story, if any? Please elaborate further below, providing specific details about the injustices faced in your story.

- *Dispossession, displacement and ocean grabbing*
- *Environmental justice concerns from pollution and waste*
- *Environmental degradation and reduction of availability of ecosystem services*
- *Undermining livelihoods of small-scale fishers*
- *Undermining access to marine resources needed for food security and well-being*
- *Inequitable distribution of economic benefits*
- *Social and cultural impacts of ocean development*
- *Marginalisation of women / non-binary persons / ethnic groups or races*
- *Human and Indigenous rights abuses*
- *Exclusion from decision making and governance*

How has the injustice(s) been mitigated/improved? Which of the following just outcomes appear in your Blue Justice story, if any? Please elaborate below. If no just outcomes are present, what outcomes would the local stakeholder(s) in the story like to see in the future?

- **Tenure & access:** *Recognising and protecting resource and spatial tenure and access rights*
- **Environmental justice:** *Taking a precautionary approach to reduce pollution and ensuring that environmental burdens are not placed on marginalised populations*
- **Ecosystem services:** *Minimising the impacts of development on habitats, resources, and ecosystem services*
- **Small-scale fisheries:** *Considering and safeguarding the access rights and livelihoods of small-scale fishers*
- **Food security:** *Maintaining and promoting access to marine resources needed for food security and well-being*
- **Economic benefits:** *Developing policies and mechanisms to foster and ensure the equitable distribution of economic benefits and/or access to marine/coastal spaces*
- **Socio-cultural impacts:** *Monitoring, mitigating and managing the social and cultural impacts of ocean development*
- **Gender equity:** *Recognising, including and promoting the equal role of women and minority groups in the ocean economy*
- **Human rights:** *Recognising and protecting human and Indigenous rights*
- **Inclusive governance:** *Developing inclusive and participatory planning and governance processes for ocean development*

Blue Justice Story Consent Form

Purpose of the activity and use of the story:

Thank you for your interest in the EmpowerUs project and potential participation in the local stories (Blue Justice stories) activity. This activity will involve collecting stories from community members about challenges they've experienced living in the coastal community of XXX (e.g. issues related to the Blue Economy, Blue Growth, marginalisation, industrial fishing, tourism, etc.), and how they have been impacted. We would like to invite you to share your story with us, along with images that reflect the story.

The story, the associated details and images provided will be collated and shared for public viewing via a StoryMap on the EmpowerUs project website. Your story may also be shared on EmpowerUs social media channels.

If you wish to share your story but would like to remain anonymous, you have the option to provide an alias instead of your real name.

Permission to use story:

I, _____ (participant's name), understand the purpose of the project activity and how the information I provide will be used. I grant permission to the EmpowerUs project to share my story and associated images publicly online.

Anonymity:

Please check the relevant box below

I grant permission to the EmpowerUs project to use my name online.

OR

I wish to remain anonymous and would like to provide an alias for my story.

Signature: _____ Date: _____

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Appendix 3: Online questionnaire that joined the Ocean & Society Survey questions with more general questions regarding empowerment from EmpowerUs.

Questions A2 to Q29 are freely available for use through the Ocean & Society Survey. Please quote McRuer et al. 2025⁷ if re-using these questions. Instructions on the use of this data, together with opportunity to join the same survey data collection tool and company (FocalData) and contribute to the overarching data sharing platform, are available on the Ocean & Society Survey website⁸. All data facilitated by these surveys are also available via this website (12 countries at the time of publishing), including the EmpowerUs facilitated surveys.

A2 (Single select)

Which of the following best describes your current gender identity?

1. Woman
2. Man
3. Non-binary and/or gender diverse
4. None of these
5. Prefer not to say

A3 (Single select)

What is your age?

1. 18 - 24
2. 25 - 34
3. 35 - 44
4. 45 - 54
5. 55 - 64
6. 65+

A4 (Single select)

Which county / municipality do you live in? (*Country specific responses*)

A5 (Single select)

What is your highest type of education?

1. Informal, home, or community-based
2. Primary / Secondary / High school
3. College or university (Diploma or Degree program)

⁷ McRuer et al. (2025). Co-designing the Ocean & Society Survey – A Global Tool for Understanding People-Ocean Connections and Mobilizing Ocean Action. *Ocean & Society*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.17645/oas.9809>

⁸ <https://oceanliteracyresearch.com/ocean-and-society-survey/>

4. Other post-secondary education (Technical, vocational, trades, or apprenticeships)
5. None of these
6. Prefer not to say

Q1 (Ranked) [Rank top 3]

In your opinion, which of the following environmental topics are of highest priority to address?

1. Climate change events (e.g., floods, heatwaves, drought)
 2. Pollution (water, soil, air)
 3. Ocean and local waterway health decline
 4. Resource decline (e.g., water, soil, wood)
 5. Overpopulation and over-development
 6. Deforestation
 7. Habitat and species loss or decline
 8. Don't know
 9. None of these
- Randomise order

Q2 (Ranked) [Rank top 3]

When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel?

1. Excited
 2. Nostalgic
 3. Awed
 4. Calm
 5. Grateful
 6. Connected
 7. Curious
 8. Anxious
 9. Fearful
 10. Unwelcome
 11. Uninterested
 12. Don't know
 13. None of these
- Randomise order

Q3 (Ranked) [Rank top 3]

When you think about the health of the ocean, how does it make you feel?

1. Hopeful
2. Motivated

3. Interested
 4. Responsible
 5. Unconcerned
 6. Angry
 7. Concerned
 8. Fearful
 9. Hopeless
 10. Uninterested
 11. Overwhelmed
 12. Uninformed
 13. Don't know
 14. None of these
- Randomise order

Q4 (Matrix - single select)

The ocean provides many benefits. How much do you value the following benefits of the ocean in your daily life?

1. Food and medicine
 2. Clean air and water
 3. Coastal protection
 4. Cultural significance
 5. Energy and resources
 6. Health and well-being
 7. Jobs and livelihood
 8. Climate protection
- Randomise order

Columns

1. No value
 2. Little value
 3. Moderate value
 4. High value
 5. Very high value
- Reverse order

Q5 (Matrix - single select)

In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean?

1. Spending time in, on, or near the ocean

2. Arts and culture (e.g., books, music, performance)
 3. Virtual technology (e.g., gaming)
 4. Educational course or activity
 5. Talking with family, friends, peers
 6. Media (e.g., print, social media, films)
 7. Public venues (e.g., museums, aquariums, libraries)
 8. Volunteering (e.g., beach cleans)
 9. Advocacy (e.g., rallies, letters, petitions)
- Randomise order

Columns

1. I have not participated
2. No change in my connection
3. A little more connected
4. More connected
5. Much more connected

Reverse order

Q6 (Multi select)

Do any of the following reasons prevent you from participating in experiences that might connect you with the ocean?

1. Cost (e.g., travel, participation, materials)
2. Lack of opportunity or awareness
3. Physical access limitations (e.g., accessibility, distance, safety)
4. Transportation limitations (e.g., public transit, pathways, travel options)
5. Digital access limitations (e.g., Internet, virtual technology, online platforms)
6. Limited resources (e.g., educational materials)
7. Lack of interest
8. Fear or discomfort
9. Lack of time
10. Government restrictions
11. Cultural or religious considerations (e.g., norms, values, traditions)
12. None of these [exclusive]

Randomise order

Q7 (Multi select)

Where do you mostly learn or get information about the ocean?

1. Formal education (e.g., schools, universities)
2. Public venues (e.g., museums, aquariums, libraries)
3. Radio or podcasts
4. Books or magazines
5. News (e.g., online, newspapers, broadcasts)
6. Social media
7. Entertainment media (e.g., films, TV shows, documentaries)
8. Research or nonprofit organization outreach (e.g., newsletters, reports)
9. Talking with family, friends, peers
10. Arts and culture (e.g., music, performance)
11. Visiting the ocean (e.g., recreation, livelihood)
12. Other
13. None of these [exclusive]

Randomise order

Choice limit: 3

Q8 (Matrix - single select)

In the past year, how often have you done the following actions?

1. Repurposed personal goods (e.g., repair, recycle)
2. Cut down on ocean-harming products (e.g., plastic bags)
3. Bought, grew, or caught sustainable food
4. Used less polluting energy (e.g., solar, hybrid vehicle)
5. Shared my opinion on ocean policies (e.g., voting, petitions)
6. Volunteered time for the ocean (e.g., beach cleanups)
7. Had conversations about the ocean with friends, family, peers
8. Donated or spent money to support the ocean
9. Supported local, sustainable businesses

Randomise order

Columns

1. Never
2. Rarely
3. Occasionally
4. Often
5. Very often

Reverse order

T1 (Text instruction) [timer: 10 seconds]

The next set of questions ask if you are willing to change your lifestyle for the ocean, and to what degree (small ways, moderate ways, big ways).

Examples of small ways: turning a tap off to brush your teeth, learning about single-use plastic, learning where food comes from

Examples of moderate ways: buying appliances that save water, buying less single-use plastic, buying sustainably-sourced food

Examples of big ways: self-restricting monthly water use, refusing any single-use plastic, becoming a vegan

Q9 (Single select)

In the next 12 months, how willing would you be to change your lifestyle if you knew it would help the ocean?

1. Not willing
2. Not very willing
3. Undecided
4. Fairly willing
5. Very willing

Reverse order

Display this question IF the answer to Q9 In the next 12 months, how will...f you knew it would help the ocean? is Fairly willing OR Very willing

Q10 (Single select)

I would be willing to change my lifestyle in...

1. Small ways
2. Moderate ways
3. Big ways

Reverse order

Display this question IF the answer to Q9 In the next 12 months, how will...f you knew it would help the ocean? is Fairly willing OR Very willing

Q11 (Multi select)

Why are you willing to change your lifestyle? Select up to 3 answers.

1. I like my lifestyle, but am willing to change
2. I know what to do, or am willing to learn
3. I have access to resources to support change
4. I believe I can make a difference and feel motivated to help
5. I find it is convenient and/or affordable
6. I'm concerned about my impact on pollution and climate change
7. I worry about future generations
8. I think ocean health is my responsibility
9. I feel if I don't make change(s), my lifestyle will be negatively impacted (e.g., money, health)
10. None of these [exclusive]

Randomise order

Choice limit: 3

Display this question IF the answer to Q9 In the next 12 months, how will...f you knew it would help the ocean? is Not very willing OR Undecided OR Not willing

Q12 (Multi select)

Why are you not willing to change your lifestyle? Select up to 3 answers.

1. I like my lifestyle and don't want to change
2. I don't know what to do, or am not willing to learn
3. I don't have access to resources to support change
4. I find it inconvenient and/or expensive
5. I feel unmotivated to help as the issues feel too big
6. I'm not concerned about my impact on pollution or climate change
7. I am willing to learn and/or have the resources to support change, but don't know where to start
8. I think we have to live for today, not worry about future generations
9. I don't think ocean health is my responsibility
10. I think technology will fix any ocean issue
11. I feel if I make change(s), my lifestyle will be negatively impacted (e.g., money, health)
12. None of these [exclusive]

Randomise order

Choice limit: 3

Q13 (Multi select)

Would any of the following incentives encourage you to make lifestyle change(s) to support ocean health? Select up to 3 answers.

1. Being provided with government resources and support
2. Feeling that I'm doing the right thing
3. Feeling that I'm helping a team or community
4. Feeling that my lifestyle will be positively impacted (e.g., money, health) if I make lifestyle changes
5. Seeing others take action (e.g., leaders, businesses, influencers, etc)
6. Understanding how my actions affect the ocean
7. Learning about issues in clear and actionable ways
8. Feeling that my lifestyle will be negatively impacted (e.g., money, health) if I don't make lifestyle changes
9. None of these [exclusive]

Randomise order

Choice limit: 3

Q14 (Matrix - single select)

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

1. The ocean is healthy
2. My daily actions influence the ocean
3. The ocean influences my daily activities
4. Ocean protection is an important step my government can take for climate action
5. Ocean protection and climate action should take priority, even at the cost of economic growth and jobs
6. Countries should work together on ocean protection, even if they disagree on other issues such as trade or security
7. My country should strengthen its commitment to protecting the ocean
8. My government is not doing enough to reduce the effects of climate change
9. Climate change is mainly due to human activity
10. Climate change is mainly due to a natural phenomenon
11. There is no climate change
12. Rich countries should give more help to poorer countries to address climate change

Randomise order

Columns

1. Disagree
 2. Slightly disagree
 3. Neither agree nor disagree
 4. Slightly agree
 5. Agree
 6. Don't know
- Reverse order

Q15 (Single select)

How often do you think about ocean health?

1. Daily
 2. Weekly
 3. Monthly
 4. A few times a year
 5. Never
 6. Don't know
- Reverse order

Q16 (Single select)

How often do you think about climate change?

1. Daily
 2. Weekly
 3. Monthly
 4. A few times a year
 5. Never
 6. Don't know
- Reverse order

Q17 (Ranked) [Rank top 3]

Which of the following threats to the ocean most concern you?

1. Plastic and marine litter
2. Pollution (e.g., spills, emissions)
3. Loss of habitats and/or species
4. Climate change
5. Overfishing
6. Offshore oil and gas drilling
7. Shipping and transportation

8. Sea level rise and coastal erosion
 9. Shoreline or coastal development
 10. Deep sea mining
 11. Don't know
 12. None of these
- Randomise order

Q18 (Matrix - single select)

In your opinion, which of the following groups need to take responsibility to address ocean threats?

1. Individuals
 2. Local communities and small businesses
 3. Government
 4. Environmental groups or non-profit organizations
 5. Industry and big businesses
 6. Indigenous leaders and communities
 7. University and research institutions
 8. Media
 9. Foundations or charities
 10. The United Nations
 11. National environmental authorities
 12. Schools and curriculum developers
- Randomise order

Columns

1. No responsibility
 2. Some responsibility
 3. Much responsibility
 4. Significant responsibility
 5. Don't know
- Reverse order

Q19 (Matrix - single select)

In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats?

1. Individuals
2. Local communities and small businesses
3. Government
4. Environmental groups or non-profit organizations

5. Industry and big businesses
6. Indigenous leaders and communities
7. Universities and research institutions
8. Media
9. Foundations or charities
10. The United Nations
11. National environmental authorities
12. Schools and curriculum developers

Randomise order

Columns

1. Do not trust at all
2. Distrust somewhat
3. Neither trust nor distrust
4. Trust somewhat
5. Trust completely
6. Don't know

Reverse order

Q20 (Ranked) [All ranked]

Here are some actions that could be taken to strengthen society's understanding of and action for the ocean. How would you rank these by importance?

1. Increasing knowledge sharing between scientists, communities, and other knowledge holders
2. Sharing and celebrating diverse cultural connections with the ocean
3. Including ocean stories in media, news, entertainment
4. Emphasizing learning about the ocean in schools and public spaces

Randomise order

T2 (Text instruction)

To help us understand ocean connections from diverse perspectives worldwide, please share a bit about yourself for research analysis and comparison. Your answers are anonymous.

Q21 (Single select)

How long have you lived in Ireland?

1. Less than 2 years
2. 3-5 years
3. More than 5 years
4. My whole life
5. My whole life, and my family has lived here for generations
6. Prefer to self-describe [text entry enabled]
7. Prefer not to say

Q22 (Single select)

How would you best describe where you live in relation to the ocean?

1. On the coast (between 0-10km or 0-6 miles from open ocean)
2. Near the coast (between 10-100km or 6-62 miles from open ocean)
3. Inland (more than 100km or 62 miles from open ocean)

Q23 (Single select)

Do you live near freshwater (e.g., walking or biking distance to lake, river, stream, wetland)?

1. Yes
2. No

Q24 (Single select)

How would you describe where you live in respect to community size?

1. Major town/city
2. Suburban (fringes of major town/city)
3. Small town or village
4. Isolated dwelling (not in town or village)
5. Prefer to self-describe [text entry enabled]
6. Prefer not to say
7. None of these

Q25 (Multi select)

Do you identify as any of the following?

1. Cultural minority
2. Ethnic minority
3. Religious minority
4. Linguistic minority

5. Refugee
 6. Immigrant
 7. Indigenous
 8. 2SLGBTQI+
 9. Person with a disability
 10. Prefer to self-describe [text entry enabled] [pinned]
 11. Prefer not to say [exclusive]
 12. None of these [exclusive]
- Randomise order

Q26 (Single select)

Which of the following employment sectors best describes your current area of work?

1. Culture, Heritage, or Tourism
 2. Education or Community Programs/Services
 3. Environmental Health
 4. Foundation or Charity
 5. Government
 6. Health and Well-being
 7. Industry or big business
 8. Media and Communication
 9. Research
 10. Retired
 11. Small business
 12. Unemployed
 13. Prefer to self-describe [text entry enabled]
 14. Prefer not to say
 15. None of these
- Choice limit: 3

Q27 (Single select)

Has your work or education focused on the environment (ocean, water, climate, other)?

1. Yes
2. No

Q28 (Single select)

What is your current annual household income, prior to tax being deducted? (note the options were standardised to be country specific)

€0 - €19,999

€20,000 - €29,999
€30,000 - €39,999
€40,000 - €49,999
€50,000 - €59,999
€60,000 - €69,999
€70,000 - €99,999
€100,000 or more
Prefer not to say

Q29 (Single select)

How did you vote in the 2024 general election (first preference), or did you not vote? (note responses were country specific, and are available via the OSS Website)

Political party 1
Political party 2
I did not vote / was not able to vote
Don't know
Prefer not to say
Randomise order

ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS FROM EMPOWERUS

(note these questions are presented in the order they appeared to the respondent. The numbers are a different order due to their use in surveys of other countries)

If re-using these questions, please quote this report (Kindlon et al., 2025)..

Q47. Do you live in a 'coastal community'?

1. Yes
2. No

T3. For the next three questions, we ask you about how prepared you feel to deal with any challenges that your local community faces. When we ask about challenges, we refer to any social, economic and /or environmental challenges.

Q48. Empowerment Dimension: Knowledge

On a scale of 1-5, where 1 is 'not at all' and 5 is 'to a very large extent', please tell us how you feel about the following statement:

"I have knowledge to overcome challenges in my community."

By knowledge we broadly mean any information to help inform your decisions and practises to face the challenges, including (but not limited to) relevant knowledge of the topic, how to use this knowledge (such where to access information, resources and who to communicate with), whether using this knowledge is ethical.

1. Not at all
2. To a small extent
3. To a moderate extent
4. To a large extent
5. To a very large extent
6. I don't know

Q50. Is there any type of knowledge you need to overcome challenges in your community? (open text)

Q51. Can you explain what sustainability means for you in 3 words? (open text)

Q53. Empowerment Dimension: Willingness

On a scale of 1-5, where 1 is 'not at all' and 5 is 'to a very large extent', please tell us how you feel about the following statement:

"I am willing to take part in actions that make my community more sustainable."

1. Not at all
2. To a small extent
3. To a moderate extent
4. To a large extent
5. To a very large extent
6. I don't know

Q52 Can you give examples of possible actions? If you are not willing, then why? (open text)

Q54. Empowerment Dimension: Access

On a scale of 1-5, where 1 is 'not at all' and 5 is 'to a very large extent', please tell us how you feel about the following statement:

"I have access to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for me as individual or my community to thrive. "

Resources could include amenities, physical materials, finances, human resources or organisational support you need.

1. Not at all
2. To a small extent
3. To a moderate extent
4. To a large extent
5. To a very large extent
6. I don't know

Q49. Cantril Ladder: Well-being

Please imagine a ladder with steps numbered from 0 at the bottom to 10 at the top. Suppose we say that the top of the ladder represents the best possible life for you and the bottom of the ladder represents the worst possible life for you. One which step of the ladder would you say that you personally feel you stand at this time, assuming that the higher the step the better you feel about your life. And the lower the step the worse you feel about it. Which step comes closest to the way you feel? (Scale / ordinal)

0 - 10

Q30 (Single select)

Thank you for taking this important survey about the ocean. Your responses are anonymous and will stay that way. They will be securely stored and may be used in future research. If you agree to use in future research, select "yes" below. If you select "no," your responses will still be securely stored for use in this research.

1. Yes
2. No

Question Behaviour Summary:

Questions with timer: T1

Questions with display logic: Q10, Q11, Q12

Exclusive responses: Q6, Q7, Q11, Q12, Q13, Q25

Pinned responses: Q25, Q29

Responses with text entry enabled: Q21, Q24, Q25, Q26

Appendix 4: Multiple linear regression model results seeking key factors related to three dimensions of empowerment of people to overcome the challenges they face: knowledge, willingness and access to resources.

47 factors (independent variables related to demographics, ocean awareness, ocean access, oceans and trust) were included in a multiple linear regression model using least squares fit to model what might influence:

- Q48: How much knowledge people feel they have to overcome challenges in their community.
- Q53: How willing people are to participate in actions that make their community more sustainable.
- Q54: How much access people feel they have to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for them as a person—or for their community—to thrive.

Table 2.1: Factors showing statistically significant relationships with how much knowledge they feel that they have to overcome challenges in their community in Bulgaria, Ireland, Finland, Norway and Spain. Results from the third iteration of a multiple linear regression model using least squares fit. Goodness-of-Fit Statistics: R^2 0.175, $p < 0.001$; f -value 0.801. β = regression coefficient, p = significance, NaN = not significant and removed from final model. $N=5155$

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
	<i>Constant</i>	-0.005	0.654
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Ireland	-0.280	<0.001
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Finland	-0.162	<0.001
Socio-demo	Q49.1 Please imagine a ladder with steps numbered from 0 at the bottom to 10 at the top. Suppose that the top of the ladder represents the best possible life for you, and the bottom represents the worst possible life for you. On which step of the ladder would you say you personally feel you are at the moment, assuming that the higher the step, the better you feel about your life, and the lower the step, the worse you feel about it? Which step is closest to how you feel? Step	0.130	<0.001
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Spain	-0.128	<0.001
Socio-demo	A16 What is your highest level of education?	0.099	<0.001
Socio-demo	Q28 What is your current household annual income, prior to tax being deducted?	0.096	<0.001

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Awareness	Q14.3 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? The ocean influences my daily activities	0.092	<0.001
Socio-demo	Q21 How long have you lived in this country?	0.061	<0.001
Access	Q5.2 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Arts and culture (e.g., books, music, performance)	0.061	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Connected	0.044	<0.01
Trust	Q19.6 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Indigenous leaders and communities	0.048	<0.01
Trust	Q19.7 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Universities and research institutions	0.046	<0.01
Access	Q5.6 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Media (e.g., print, social media, films)	0.044	<0.01
Access	Q5.1 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Spending time in, on, or near the ocean	0.041	<0.01
Socio-demo	Q27 Has your work or education focused on the environment (ocean, water, climate, other)?	0.037	<0.01
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Excited	0.033	<0.01
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Bulgaria	-0.065	<0.05
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Norway	-0.061	<0.05
Socio-demo	Q22 How would you best describe where you live in relation to the ocean?	-0.033	<0.05
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Awed	0.029	<0.05
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Curious	0.027	<0.05
Socio-demo	A2 Which of the following best describes your current gender identity?	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A3 What is your age?	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Nostalgic	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Calm	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Grateful	NaN	NaN

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Anxious	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Fearful	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Unwelcome	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Uninterested	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.3 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Virtual technology (e.g., gaming)	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.4 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Educational course or activity	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.5 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Talking with family, friends, peers	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.7 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Public venues (e.g., museums, aquariums, libraries)	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.8 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Volunteering (e.g., beach cleans)	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.9 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Advocacy (e.g., rallies, letters, petitions)	NaN	NaN
Awareness	Q14.2 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? My daily actions influence the ocean	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.1 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Individuals	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.2 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Local communities and small businesses	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.3 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Government	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.4 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Environmental groups or non-profit organizations	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.5 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Industry and big businesses	NaN	NaN

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Trust	Q19.8 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Media	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.9 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Foundations or charities	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.10 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? The United Nations	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.11 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? National environmental authorities	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.12 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Schools and curriculum developers	NaN	NaN

¹ A β -coefficient of 1 would mean that for a one standard deviation increase in this factor, the response variable (willingness) is predicted to increase by one standard deviation, holding all other variables constant.

Table 2.2: Factors showing statistically significant relationships with willingness of people to participate in actions that make their community more sustainable in Bulgaria, Ireland, Finland, Norway and Spain. Results from the third iteration of a multiple linear regression model using least squares fit. Goodness-of-Fit Statistics: R^2 0.233, $p < 0.001$; f-value 0.759. β = regression coefficient, p = significance, NaN = not significant and removed from final model. N=5227

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
	<i>Constant</i>	-0.005	0.654
Access	Q5.8 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Volunteering (e.g., beach cleans)	0.128	<0.001
Awareness	Q14.2 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? My daily actions influence the ocean	0.118	<0.001
Awareness	Q14.3 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? The ocean influences my daily activities	0.103	<0.001
Trust	Q19.4 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Environmental groups or non-profit organizations	0.087	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Anxious	0.074	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Grateful	0.072	<0.001

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Finland	-0.065	<0.001
Trust	Q19.3 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Government	-0.065	<0.001
Socio-demo	Q21 How long have you lived in this country?	0.063	<0.001
Socio-demo	A16 What is your highest level of education?	0.063	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Excited	0.062	<0.001
Trust	Q19.7 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Universities and research institutions	0.057	<0.001
Socio-demo	Q49.1 Please imagine a ladder with steps numbered from 0 at the bottom to 10 at the top. Suppose that the top of the ladder represents the best possible life for you, and the bottom represents the worst possible life for you. On which step of the ladder would you say you personally feel you are at the moment, assuming that the higher the step, the better you feel about your life, and the lower the step, the worse you feel about it? Which step is closest to how you feel? Step	0.056	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Curious	0.055	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Fearful	0.054	<0.001
Socio-demo	Q28 What is your current household annual income, prior to tax being deducted?	0.052	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Awed	0.052	<0.001
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Connected	0.052	<0.001
Access	Q5.5 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Talking with family, friends, peers	0.050	<0.01
Access	Q5.9 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Advocacy (e.g., rallies, letters, petitions)	0.055	<0.01
Socio-demo	A3 What is your age?	-0.041	<0.01
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Calm	0.041	<0.01
Access	Q5.1 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Spending time in, on, or near the ocean	0.040	<0.05

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Trust	Q19.6 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Indigenous leaders and communities	0.033	<0.05
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Uninterested	-0.031	<0.05
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Bulgaria	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Ireland	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Norway	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Spain	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A2 Which of the following best describes your current gender identity?	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Nostalgic	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Unwelcome	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.2 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Arts and culture (e.g., books, music, performance)	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.3 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Virtual technology (e.g., gaming)	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.4 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Educational course or activity	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.6 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Media (e.g., print, social media, films)	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.7 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Public venues (e.g., museums, aquariums, libraries)	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.1 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Individuals	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.2 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Local communities and small businesses	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.5 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Industry and big businesses	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.8 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Media	NaN	NaN

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Trust	Q19.9 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Foundations or charities	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.10 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? The United Nations	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.11 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? National environmental authorities	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.12 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Schools and curriculum developers	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	Q22 How would you best describe where you live in relation to the ocean?	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	Q27 Has your work or education focused on the environment (ocean, water, climate, other)?	NaN	NaN

¹ A β -coefficient of 1 would mean that for a one standard deviation increase in this factor, the response variable (willingness) is predicted to increase by one standard deviation, holding all other variables constant.

Table 2.3: Factors showing statistically significant relationships with how much access people feel they have to resources such as tools, opportunities, and support that are necessary for them as a person—or for their community—to thrive. in Bulgaria, Ireland, Finland, Norway and Spain.

Results from the third iteration of a multiple linear regression model using least squares fit.

Goodness-of-Fit Statistics: R^2 0.188, $p < 0.001$; f-value 0.767. β = regression coefficient, p = significance, NaN = not significant and removed from final model. N=4987

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
	<i>Constant</i>	<i>0.018</i>	<i>0.152</i>
Socio-demo	Q49.1 Please imagine a ladder with steps numbered from 0 at the bottom to 10 at the top. Suppose that the top of the ladder represents the best possible life for you, and the bottom represents the worst possible life for you. On which step of the ladder would you say you personally feel you are at the moment, assuming that the higher the step, the better you feel about your life, and the lower the step, the worse you feel about it? Which step is closest to how you feel? Step	0.201	<0.001
Access	Q5.4 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Educational course or activity	0.109	<0.001
Awareness	Q14.3 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? The ocean influences my daily activities	0.105	<0.001

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Norway	0.079	<0.001
Socio-demo	Q28 What is your current household annual income, prior to tax being deducted?	0.074	<0.001
Socio-demo	A3 What is your age?	-0.068	<0.001
Access	Q5.3 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Virtual technology (e.g., gaming)	0.065	<0.001
Access	Q5.1 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Spending time in, on, or near the ocean	-0.063	<0.001
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Spain	0.056	<0.001
Socio-demo	A16 What is your highest level of education?	0.053	<0.001
Trust	Q19.2 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Local communities and small businesses	0.051	<0.001
Access	Q5.2 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Arts and culture (e.g., books, music, performance)	0.059	<0.01
Trust	Q19.6 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Indigenous leaders and communities	0.050	<0.01
Access	Q5.9 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Advocacy (e.g., rallies, letters, petitions)	0.042	<0.05
Socio-demo	Q27 Has your work or education focused on the environment (ocean, water, climate, other)?	0.030	<0.05
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Bulgaria	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Finland	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A1 Market: Ireland	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	A2 Which of the following best describes your current gender identity?	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Excited	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Nostalgic	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Awed	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Calm	NaN	NaN

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Grateful	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Connected	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Curious	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Anxious	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Fearful	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Unwelcome	NaN	NaN
Emocean	Q2 When you think about the ocean, how does it make you feel? Uninterested	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.5 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Talking with family, friends, peers	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.6 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Media (e.g., print, social media, films)	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.7 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Public venues (e.g., museums, aquariums, libraries)	NaN	NaN
Access	Q5.8 In the past year, have any of the following experiences made you feel more connected to the ocean? Volunteering (e.g., beach cleans)	NaN	NaN
Awareness	Q14.2 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? My daily actions influence the ocean	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.1 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Individuals	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.3 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Government	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.4 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Environmental groups or non-profit organizations	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.5 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Industry and big businesses	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.7 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Universities and research institutions	NaN	NaN

Type	Factor (independent variable)	β^1	p
Trust	Q19.8 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Media	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.9 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Foundations or charities	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.10 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? The United Nations	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.11 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? National environmental authorities	NaN	NaN
Trust	Q19.12 In your opinion, to what extent do you trust each of the following groups to take action to address ocean threats? Schools and curriculum developers	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	Q21 How long have you lived in this country?	NaN	NaN
Socio-demo	Q22 How would you best describe where you live in relation to the ocean?	NaN	NaN

¹ A β -coefficient of 1 would mean that for a one standard deviation increase in this factor, the response variable (willingness) is predicted to increase by one standard deviation, holding all other variables constant.

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